

Master Thesis

Exploring modularity on innovative IT partnerships: The art of balancing autonomy and collaboration

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Executive Summary

This thesis explores the dynamics of strategic innovation within enterprises, specifically focusing on **innovative IT partnerships**. Traditionally, IT innovation was often pursued through outsourcing, but this approach has faced significant challenges, partly due to issues related to modularity. Traditional IT outsourcing contracts, rooted in transactional agreements, often limit innovation due to their focus on clear, predictable outcomes and risk reduction, which is incompatible with the inherent unpredictability of innovation. This has led to a noticeable **shift from transaction-based engagements towards innovative partnerships**. While research exists on traditional outsourcing, there is a lack of knowledge on the strategic innovation aspect of innovative IT partnerships from both managerial and structural perspectives.

The central research question guiding this thesis is: **What is the influence of modularity on the adaptability of innovative IT partnerships?** This question is broken down into three sub-questions focusing on relevant change drivers, the construction model of an innovative IT partnership, and the impact of modularity on its quality attributes. The core idea is that innovation is unpredictable, and thus, partnerships must be adaptable or "evolvable".

Modularity is presented as a design principle for creating structures that enable adaptability. **Normalized Systems Theory (NST)** is introduced as a theory and set of design principles for creating evolvable systems, aiming to prevent ripple and combinatorial effects when changes occur.

The research employed a **Design Science Research approach**, combining theoretical exploration with practical insights. The methodology involved three steps: identifying relevant change drivers through an **expert panel**, developing a structured artefact for selected change drivers, and evaluating and refining this artefact through **individual expert interviews**. Experts were selected based on extensive experience in innovative IT partnerships from various industries and countries.

Key results include the identification and consolidation of relevant **change drivers** for innovative IT partnerships by the expert panel. Three change drivers were selected for in-depth analysis due to their high variability among expert opinions and clear modular aspects: **Strategic Shift, Leaving Partner, and New Partner**. The thesis also proposes and partially validates a construction model for innovative IT partnerships, drawing on DEMO theory, which focuses on the objective internal structure rather than functions.

A significant finding regarding the impact of modularity (NST) on partnership quality attributes is the identification of coherence between measures based on NST theorems and managerial measures. For instance, applying NST principles like **Separation of Concerns (SoC)** and **Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC)** to partnership components (like partners, shared objectives, and capabilities) can inform managerial measures such as periodic synchronization meetings to align interests and manage changes. However, the research also revealed contradictory findings, suggesting that the strict separation or distribution of capabilities, as implied by some NST principles, might hinder the collaboration and knowledge sharing necessary for innovation in partnerships.

This leads to a key implication: while NST can help align partner and partnership interests (especially through managing CCC and SoC), its traditional role of minimizing ripple effects might actually **hinder innovation** in partnerships by creating barriers to essential collaboration and interdependency. The research highlights the **tension between the need for partner autonomy (supported by modularity) and the need for interdependency (essential for collaboration and synergy)** in innovative IT partnerships. Successfully managing this balance is crucial.

The thesis contributes to science by applying NST (an example of **exaptation**) to the new domain of innovative IT partnerships, developing a construction model based on DEMO, collecting initial change drivers and measures, and offering a multi-faceted view. For practice, it provides a valuable artefact and illustrated examples for systematically analysing modular aspects of partnerships, confirmed as useful by experts.

Limitations include the qualitative nature of the findings due to the limited number and potential bias of experts, the high variability in change driver definitions, and the partial validation of the construction model. Future research could complete the collection of change drivers and measures, explore different perspectives (e.g., anti-fragility), investigate modularity in the implementation of innovation within partnerships, and formally validate the entire construction model.

In conclusion, applying modularity principles, particularly through NST, offers a structured approach to analysing and enhancing the evolvability of innovative IT partnerships. However, the tension between fostering partner autonomy and maintaining the necessary interdependency for innovation requires a careful balancing act.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Acknowledgements.....	4
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Background	9
1.1.1 Problem statement.....	9
1.2 Research question.....	9
1.2.1 Relevance of the research questions	9
1.3 Conceptual model.....	10
1.4 Reading guide.....	10
2 Theoretical background	12
2.1 Key concepts	12
2.1.1 Innovation	12
2.1.2 Innovative collaboration	13
2.1.3 Unpredictable.....	13
2.1.4 Evolvability.....	13
2.1.5 Value of Modularity (black-box)	14
2.2 Change Drivers.....	15
2.2.1 Introduction.....	15
2.2.2 External change drivers of partnerships.....	16
2.2.3 Internal change drivers of partnerships.....	18
2.3 Applying Modularity (white-box).....	19
2.3.1 Principles of modularity.....	19
2.3.2 Modular architecture	20
2.3.3 Normalized Systems Theory	21
2.3.4 Exaptation	23
2.4 Function of a partnership.....	24
2.4.1 Transactional collaboration.....	24
2.4.2 Innovative partnerships definition	27
2.4.3 Comparing : Traditional collaboration versus Innovative Partnership	29
2.5 Construction of a partnership (white-box)	30
2.5.1 Construction of a partnership.....	30
2.5.2 Elements of construction.....	31

3	Research Design and Approach.....	34
3.1	Methodology	34
3.2	Research design.....	34
3.2.1	Research Scope	34
3.2.2	Research Approach	35
3.3	Step 1: Panel discussion.....	35
3.3.1	Panel Preparation	35
3.3.2	Panel discussion / Collecting the experts’ opinions.....	36
3.4	Step 2: Proposed artefact.....	36
3.5	Step 3: Evaluation artefact	38
4	Research Results.....	39
4.1	Step 1: Experts Panel Results.....	39
4.1.1	Change drivers	39
4.1.2	Consolidated change drivers	41
4.1.3	Impact of change drivers.....	41
4.1.4	Mitigation and cultivation of impact of change drivers.....	43
4.2	Step 2: Preparation Artefact	43
4.3	Step 3: Expert sessions – demonstrate artefact	43
4.3.1	Change driver: Strategic shift	44
4.3.2	Change driver: Leaving partner	46
4.3.3	Change driver: New partner.....	49
5	Discussion.....	52
5.1	Interpretation of findings.....	52
5.1.1	RQ1: Relevant Change Drivers	52
5.1.2	RQ2: Construction of innovative partnership.....	52
5.1.3	RQ3: Impact modularity on quality attributes of partnership.....	53
5.1.4	Implications – The art of balancing autonomy and collaboration	55
5.2	Contributions.....	56
5.2.1	Contribution to science	56
5.2.2	Contribution to practice	56
5.3	Limitations	57
5.4	Suggestions for future research.....	57
5.5	Reflections.....	58
5.5.1	Perspective by Bernard de Veer	58

5.5.2	Perspective by Serge van Nimwegen.....	58
6	Conclusion.....	59
	Appendix A: References	61
	Appendix B: List of Tables	72
	Appendix C: List of Figures	73
	Appendix D: Artefacts	74
	Change driver: Strategic Shift.....	74
	Change driver: Leaving partner.....	74
	Change driver: New partner	75
	Appendix E: Research results - Construction model	76
	Appendix F: Research results - Measures based on NST and Managerial measures	78
	Appendix G: List of Abbreviations.....	82
	Appendix H: Recordings expert panel and expert interviews	83

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

This thesis explores strategic innovation within enterprises, emphasizing the role of IT as both an enabler and accelerator of their competitive advantage. Initially, these innovations were driven by IT outsourcing, which could positively impact the enterprise in stable and predictable environments. However, many IT outsourcing projects continue to face significant challenges and risks (Könning et al., 2019; Varajão et al., 2017). These issues might stem from underlying problems related to modularity aspects (Benazeer et al., 2024a; Huysmans, Bruyn, et al., 2014). One approach to addressing these modularity issues is through the lens of Normalized Systems Theory (NST), particularly its application to innovative IT partnerships to enhance evolvability.

1.1.1 Problem statement

Strategic innovations play a crucial role in significantly enhancing a client's overall competitiveness (Weeks and Feeny, 2008; Lacity and Willcocks, 2013; Oshri et al., 2015; Su et al., 2016). As the strategic importance of IT continues to grow (Kranz, 2021), there is an increasing need for access to specialized skills and innovative solutions (Kranz, 2021). The limitations mentioned in traditional outsourcing contracts hampered innovation, i.e. 'Innovation in IT Outsourcing' Paradox (Kranz, 2021). This evolution is reflected in the changing nature of outsourcing relationships (Kranz, 2021), where there is a noticeable shift from transaction-based engagements towards innovative partnerships (Susarla and Mukhopadhyay, 2019).

While much research has been done on traditional transactional IT outsourcing, there is a lack of knowledge on the strategic innovation part of innovative IT Partnerships, both from a managerial point of view as well as from a structural point of view.

Problem Statement

Traditional agreements in partnerships impose constraints on innovative collaborations, limiting their potential to foster creativity and adaptability.

1.2 Research question

*What is the influence of **modularity** on the **adaptability** of **innovative IT partnerships**?*

RQ1: What are relevant **change drivers** for **innovative IT partnerships**?

RQ2: What is the **construction** model of an **innovative IT partnership** ?

RQ3: What is the impact of modularity on **quality attributes** of an **innovative IT partnership**?

1.2.1 Relevance of the research questions

Traditional IT outsourcing contracts often faced limitations in fostering innovation (Kranz, 2021). The competitive landscape is shifting from transactional engagements to innovative partnerships (Gambal et al., 2022; Susarla & Mukhopadhyay, 2019). Strategic innovations

can significantly enhance an enterprise's overall competitiveness (Gambal et al., 2022; Lacity & Willcocks, 2013; Oshri et al., 2015; Su et al., 2015; Weeks & Feeny, 2008).

While there has been an increase in the strategic importance of IT (Kranz, 2021) and the necessity for specialized skills and innovation (Kranz, 2021), research is predominantly focused on the initial phases (Antecedents and Arrangements). However, there is limited research on the Generation and Outcomes phases (Gambal et al., 2022).

Outsourcing partnerships are evolving (Kranz, 2021). Despite this evolution, there is a scarcity of literature on innovative partnerships that could adapt to various change drivers. It is crucial to minimize ripple effects or combinatorial impacts to reduce the adverse effects on innovative IT partnerships.

1.3 Conceptual model

Figure 1-1 Conceptual Model

Change drivers: An aspect of a system that was expected to change independently of other aspects. Includes everything that could change for different reasons, at different times, and at different rates (Haerens, 2024; Martin et al., 2018; Mannaert et al., 2016).

Innovative IT Partnerships: The partnership was a relationship in which two or more people, organizations or countries work together as partners. (Kiss, 2020) Parties had a vested interest in each other's success (Gambal et al, 2022)

Normalized Systems Theory: a theory and set of design principles for creating evolvable information systems (Mannaert et al., 2016).

1.4 Reading guide

This paragraph described the structure of this thesis. This thesis journey starts with a process of exploration with a diverging phase on various topics and approaches. This is followed by a converging phase resulting in this document. We start by describing the problem statement and related research questions in the introduction chapter (chapter one), followed by key concepts from the existing literature in chapter two. The research design and approach are described in chapter three including a proposed artefact. This is followed by an overview of the expert panel and individual expert interviews resulting in a collection of change drivers as well as validated artefacts in chapter four. Chapter five interprets these results by comparing

these results to the existing literature (chapter two) which results in confirmation on certain topics but also some contradictory findings. We also mention limitations, contributions, opportunities for future research and some personal reflections in chapter five. Chapter six concluded this thesis.

2 Theoretical background

Successful partnerships are not a matter of chance. Innovation is unpredictable, so partnerships must be adaptable. Currently, partnerships are often viewed from a legal perspective. This thesis examines partnerships from an evolvability standpoint, using modularity to describe the structures that enable adaptability within a partnership. These partnerships are affected by change drivers that can have either negative impacts (requiring mitigation measures) or positive impacts (enabling cultivation measures).

2.1 Key concepts

Innovation cannot be predicted. As it is not predictable, it should be evolvable. To be evolvable a system must be modular.

Partnerships are not predictable. As an important means for innovation, they must be evolvable too.

Figure 2-1 Relations between innovation and modularity

Innovation by transactional relationships is not possible, hence partnerships!

We look from a lens of modularity, not from legal or management.

Figure 2-2 Innovation by partnerships

2.1.1 Innovation

Innovation is the development and implementation of new ideas to solve problems (Dosi, 1988). It can be achieved by combining knowledge and technologies in novel ways (Carnabuci & Bruggeman, 2009; Fleming & Sorenson, 2001) or by recombining existing technologies to develop new functions (Henderson & Clark, 1990; Yayavaram & Ahuja, 2008).

This research will focus on new products, processes, services, or business models that facilitate new market entries that are fundamentally new to client firms or their customers. These innovations are linked to the core business (Oshri et al., 2015; Droege et al., 2009; Weeks & Feeny, 2008).

2.1.2 Innovative collaboration

This study looked at collaboration as a means of achieving innovation. It distinguished between two collaboration types: (1) transactional relationship and (2) partnership.

Transactional collaboration is widely used within outsourcing. Here, the client has clearly defined what the vendor must deliver and is suitable for predictable outcomes. This makes this type of collaboration unsuitable for innovation, also known as the ITO paradox (Aubert et al., 2015).

Innovative partnerships are based on trust and interdependency. The focus is on what is in it for us where the partnership as a vehicle is the most important one. Partnerships are therefore well suited to innovation as the outcome is unpredictable (Kishore et al., 2003; Mehta & Mehta, 2010; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

2.1.3 Unpredictable

Innovation is unpredictable for several interconnected reasons. This originates from the complex interplay of technological components and the inherent uncertainty associated with novel and breakthrough inventions (Fleming & Sorenson, 2001).

2.1.4 Evolvability

When innovations are unpredictable it means that not only current requirements must be supported, but also unknown future requirements. To support these changes a partnership should be designed to accommodate future changes to allow the partnership to evolve over time.

Figure 2-3 Evolvability, Flexibility, Variability (van Nuffel, 2011)

Before using the concept of evolvability it is important to describe what this concept means. The term evolvability is often used interchangeably with flexibility and variability while they are not the same. Van Nuffel (2011) defines the differences between the concepts:

Concepts	Description
Evolvability	Evolvability is linked to “artefact mutability” which refers to anticipated changes over time.
Flexibility	Describes general ability to adapt across different dimensions (time, cost, effort).
Variability	Property of being changeable. Describes inherent changeable nature of an object and its potential points of variation (location where variation might occur). Depending on the artefact different properties of change exist. E.g. attribute, logic, workflow, interface and persistency variability.

Table 2-1 Differences between flexibility, variability and evolvability (van Nuffel, 2011)

The variability refers to the properties of an object being changeable (Eijndhoven et al., 2008). These properties refer to variation points, which are locations of an object where the variation occurs. Also referred to as Change drivers (see paragraph 2.2).

Focus of this research is effort and contained impact of making changes to a designed artefact, like a partnership. Flexibility by design. Time and Cost of flexibility is of less importance. Goal is to decrease the effort for changing. Evolvability is linked to “artefact mutability” which refers to the anticipated changes over time.

These concepts and definition describe the desired criteria for this research. Modularity in partnerships should result in the absence of ripple effects or combinatorial effects when exposed to identified change drivers, defined in paragraph 2.2. This is not only applicable for innovation as an outcome of a partnership, but also for the partnership itself.

2.1.5 Value of Modularity (black-box)

Modularity refers to a design principle to decompose a system in loosely coupled building blocks (Simon, 1962). A distinction can be made between modularity as a process, which involves decomposing a complex system into a collection of components, and a modular architecture, where the interactions between modules are weak but not negligible (Simon, 1962, p. 474). In this thesis the lens of modular architecture is used. Building blocks are designed to hide (complex) design decisions from others and to support independent development of every building block (Parnas, 1972). The aim of modularity is to maximise interdependence within building blocks and minimize interdependence between building blocks (Campagnolo & Camuffo, 2010; Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Langlois & Robertson, 1992). This corresponds with an important design rule of low coupling, high cohesion (Ethiraj & Levinthal, 2004).

Modular design is a useful means to manage complexity (Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Ethiraj & Levinthal, 2004) and is applied in many disciplines (E.g. engineering, design sciences, system sciences, computer science, management and supply chain management) and is the cornerstone of engineering (De Bruyn & Mannaert, 2012; Campagnolo & Camuffo, 2010; Simon, 1996; Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Schilling, 2000; Simon, 1962). The literature review of Campagnolo and Camuffo (2010) gives a comprehensive overview of the value of modularity in product, production system and organizational modularity.

Modular structures provide a number of advantages: e.g., an increase in innovation (Baldwin & Clark, 1997), increase of flexibility in product development (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2016), an increase in design options (Baldwin & Clark, 2000) and the creation of strategic flexibility in

product architecture (Sanchez & Shibata, 2021). Product modularization leads to greater levels of buyer-supplier collaboration (Howard & Squire, 2007).

Besides the advantages of modularity is also has some side effects. Modularization allows to address specific system properties in an isolated way. However, modularization might result in imitation (Ethiraj et al., 2008) and cause a loss in the enterprise's market share as happened with IBM System /360 (Baldwin & Clark, 1997). High modularity also might reduce knowledge sharing because it generally decreases the need for interaction and collaboration between components due to well defined interfaces (Ven et al., 2010).

Designing proper modularity is a balancing act. It requires a deep understanding of the system's interdependencies, a careful consideration of the trade-offs between modularity and integration, and often an iterative approach to refine the design over time. Modularity has benefits but applying too much modularity can lead to suboptimal outcomes (Ethiraj & Levinthal, 2004). Absence of omniscience in design means that choices about modules are essentially educated guesses about appropriate decompositions (Ethiraj & Levinthal, 2004).

For the design of modular systems Normalized Systems Theory is used (Mannaert et al., 2016). An evolvable system is defined by its change drivers. Modularity creates structure and a system to define proper modularity. Modularity defines relation between multiple aspects of a partnership. E.g. shared objectives and shared value, relations, industry, subject of collaboration, business model, regulations.

2.2 Change Drivers

2.2.1 Introduction

In the previous paragraph, the concept of change is mentioned several times. In the context of innovation, the evolvability of a system (e.g. IT systems, group of partners in a partnership) is important. This makes it essential for a system to be adaptable. Although it is not possible to define the specific changes that might occur in an innovation process (Fleming & Sorenson, 2001) or the impact on architecture (Lassing et al., 2003), it is possible to predict the types of change that could emerge. This is also where the concept of "change drivers" originates. This paragraph discusses which change drivers are relevant for partnerships and might cause changes that a partnership should be equipped to address.

To the best of our ability, we did not find literature regarding change drivers of partnerships. However, partnerships share many similarities with organizational change. This paragraph provides an overview of various change drivers at the organizational level.

Changes can be divided into first- and second-order change processes (Ethiraj & Levinthal, 2004). First-order change refers to incremental local changes within an existing organization structure. E.g., Changes in pricing policies, product launches, changes in investments in research and development or advertising. This type of change aims at improving performance and finding stable solutions within the existing design. Second-order changes represent changes in the underlying organizational structure itself. Fundamental shifts in strategy or organization structure are also classified as second-order change. Second-order changes are in scope for this research.

A Change Driver causes a change in a system and can be either external or internal. The cause of this change can come from many factors such as technology, market trends, regulatory changes or competitive pressures (Porter, 1979). A single change driver corresponds to a single concern in a system (Mannaert et al., 2016, p. 274) and includes everything that can change of different reasons, at different times, and at different rates (Haerens, 2024). This principle was informally described by Parnas already in (1972) as what was later called *design for change*. The concept of change drivers are used in multiple fields to understand changes in supply chain management (Istanbouli, 2024), document management (Oorts et al., 2017) and business process modeling (Nuffel et al., 2010).

A change driver is strongly related to the NS principle Separation of Concern (Mannaert et al., 2016) and will be further discussed in paragraph 2.3.3.

In this paragraph, common change drivers that frequently occur in partnerships are discussed. These change drivers highlight the aspects of a partnership that must be adaptable to effectively manage change. Additionally, the construction of the partnership (refer to paragraph 2.5) must be capable of accommodating these changes.

In the context of innovative IT partnerships, achieving stability and adaptability is essential. The environment in which partnerships operate, as well as the internal dynamics of the partnership, will inevitably change and evolve over time. Therefore, understanding and managing change drivers is crucial for maintaining the effectiveness and adaptability of innovative partnerships.

In literature no research has been found regarding change drivers for partnerships. Research exists regarding quality attributes of successful partnerships (Kranz, 2021; Lane & Lum, 2011; Mehta & Mehta, 2010; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012). Several characteristics have positive contributions to successful partners such as mutual trust (Gambal et al., 2022; Kranz, 2021; Lane & Lum, 2011; Mehta & Mehta, 2010; Vitasek et al., 2013), shared values (Gambal et al., 2022; Kramer & Porter, 2011; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012) and collaboration (Gambal et al., 2022; Kranz, 2021; Mehta & Mehta, 2010; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

Many of the aforementioned attributes don't have strong modular properties or are challenging to quantify. In the field of modularity, it is important to clearly define concerns and minimize interdependencies due to poorly defined concerns.

2.2.2 External change drivers of partnerships

For the definition of external change drivers the competitive forces model (Porter, 1979) is used. In the environment of an innovative partnerships multiple change drivers can be distinguished. The ability of partnerships to adapt to these external change drivers, such as technological advancements, is crucial for their longevity (Ungureanu et al., 2018).

The following change drivers can be distinguished which are based on the competitive forces model (Porter, 1979) and esteem then these change drivers are applicable for innovative partnerships.

Figure 2-4 Competitive forces model (Porter, 1979)

Threat of new entrants: new competition

Entry of new competitors with innovative technologies can reduce market share and erode profitability of the partnership.

Modular partnerships might be able to quickly adapt and develop new components. Partners can independently develop new modules to enhance the product.

Threat of new entrants: Regulatory and compliance changes

Entering a new market can make a partnership have to comply with regulation that raises costs. Regulations might increase the complexity and cost of innovation. Examples of regulatory changes are GDPR and NIS2. The consequence of GDPR might be the limitation of data collection which are crucial for research and development and the increased compliance costs can hamper innovation efforts and divert resources away from innovation activities. NIS2 results in increased regulatory burden and compliance costs. Companies must invest in advanced cybersecurity measures, reporting mechanisms, and regulatory security audits. This is particularly challenging for partnerships with limited budgets and resources.

Threat of substitute products or services: Technological advancements

New technologies offering similar functionalities at lower cost can make the partnership obsolete. A shift in consumer behaviour towards alternative technologies can decrease demand for products or services developed by the partnership.

In a modular partnership partners might independently develop new product features and maintaining competitive advantage.

Bargaining power of buyers:

When buyers face low switching cost they might easily move to competitors and eroding the potential partnership's customer base.

Modular partnerships can segment their offerings to support different buyer needs. Each partner can focus on specific modules that align with buyer demands. This modular approach helps to effectively manage buyer expectations.

Bargaining power of suppliers: Change in cost or price

Suppliers can exert bargaining power by raising prices, which may necessitate the exploration of alternative technologies, specialists, or licenses to maintain cost efficiency, especially when dealing with critical resources. The ease with which technology can be replaced plays a significant role in ensuring the continuity of a partnership.

Modular partnerships can diversify their partners by assigning different partners to specific capabilities. This reduces dependency on any single partner and ensures continuity in case of disruptions.

Market competition

This force is about competitive rivalry in industry. These forces can be the number of competitors, similar offerings, high fixed costs and the size of the industry.

This strength is especially relevant when it is decided to set up a partnership. This phase of the partnership is beyond the scope of this study.

2.2.3 Internal change drivers of partnerships

To the best of our ability, we did not find any literature on internal change drivers of partnerships.

A partnership is constructed based on several components. Changes can occur on these components that the partnership must be able to deal with. The following paragraphs describes the components and possible related change drivers.

Partner dynamics: new partner

New partners may join because of missing knowledge or technology or new opportunities which emerge in the market. This might result in additional knowledge and expertise (Kranz, 2021).

Partner dynamics: leaving partner

Partners may leave the partnership due to several reasons. Some examples are change of strategic focus of the partnership, financial issues and disagreements or changes in key personnel (Alajoutsijärvi et al., 2000).

Strategic shift of partnership

Due to external or internal influences the tactical direction must be altered (Alajoutsijärvi et al., 2000).

Capability

Access to knowledge, expertise, technology and departure of key personnel (Alajoutsijärvi et al., 2000; Levina & Vaast, 2005).

2.3 Applying Modularity (white-box)

Modularity is a fundamental principle in systems design that emphasizes breaking down a complex system into smaller, manageable components or modules, each with a well-defined function. This approach allows organizations to achieve high cohesion within modules while minimizing interdependencies between them, ensuring flexibility, scalability, and ease of maintenance. By adopting modularity, enterprises can enhance their ability to adapt to changes, streamline communication channels, and optimize resources. This paragraph describes how modularity can be effectively applied highlighting key principles like low coupling, high cohesion, and clear interfaces.

2.3.1 Principles of modularity

Modularity is a property of a system which advocates designing structure to maximise interdependence within building blocks and minimize interdependence between building blocks (Campagnolo & Camuffo, 2010; Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Langlois & Robertson, 1992). This is also known as high cohesion and low coupling. This is realized by a design which hides (complex) design decisions from others and supports independent development of every building block (Parnas, 1972).

Good modular design is characterised by the following principles:

- a) **Dependency and coupling** (Benazeer, De Beuckelaer, Verelst, Manneart, Huysmans, 2012)
- b) **Low coupling (or low inter-modular coupling)** (Benazeer et al., 2024). Modules should be able to function independently with minimum dependencies.
- c) **High cohesion (or low intra-modular cohesion)** (Huysmans et al., 2014). A module encompasses all necessary components and responsibilities to execute a specific task.
- d) **Clear Interfaces:** Modules should have clear input and output interfaces (Langlois, 2002).
- e) **Coupling:** is not just about counting arrows between modules, but mainly about the nature of the connection. I.e., whether ripple effects pass through or not (Mannaert et al., 2016)
- f) **Cohesion:** not just about splitting into a sea of modules, but also about the hierarchical aggregation of related modules (Mannaert et al., 2016)

“based on a thorough understanding of the underlying mechanisms, both concepts are about coupling and the avoidance of ripple effects: low intra-modular coupling, known as high cohesion, low inter-modular coupling, known as low coupling. Moreover, the concepts of coupling and cohesion are refined. Coupling between modules is not just about counting arrows, but mainly about the nature of the connection, i.e., whether ripple effects pass through or not. Cohesion is not just about splitting into a sea of modules, but also about the hierarchical aggregation of related modules.” (Mannaert et al., 2016)

2.3.1.1 Cohesion

Cohesion is about grouping of connected or interrelated parts in a module. High cohesion means that elements within a module are closely related and work together to achieve a specific goal. **A module should have a single, well-defined purpose.** Software design principles like Single Responsibility Principle (SRP) and Separation of Concerns (SoC), advocate for high cohesion (Martin et al., 2018).

2.3.1.2 Coupling

Coupling is a concept related to the degree of interdependence between one or more modules. A low degree of coupling should be achieved to minimize dependencies which decrease the evolvability and maintainability of systems (Benazeer et al., 2012).

This means that modules are structurally independent of each other but work together in a larger system. This system must have an architecture that creates “both independence of structure and integration of functions” (Baldwin & Clark, 2000).

Low coupling implies that modules depend on each other minimally. Changes to one module should have minimal impact on other modules.

Unleashing the exponential variation gains, without mastering the coupling that entails the exponential ripple costs, may destroy the evolvability (Mannaert et al., 2016).

2.3.2 Modular architecture

Because modularity is used in so many different places, different applications can be discerned. A distinction can be made between modularity purely as a process of decomposition of a complex system into a collection of components or a modular design to design an evolvable system. This thesis focuses on the latter in the context of innovative partnerships.

Tiwana and Konsynski (2010, p. 288) define architectural modularity as the degree to which an architecture is decomposed into relatively independent subsystems. These subsystems are atomic, fine-grained units of functionality which can be software components, modules, objects, or services, and they can be easily combined with other modules to construct new processes. Furthermore, Tiwana and Konsynski (2010) defined IT architecture modularity as “the degree of decomposition of an organization's IT portfolio into loosely coupled subsystems that communicate through standardized interfaces.” They highlight standardization and loose coupling, characterized by a high degree of independence between modules, as two key constructs of IT architecture modularity.

Even though modularity can make an important contribution to reducing complexity and increasing flexibility, modular architecture alone is not enough. Modularity must reflect an organization's required business objectives and dynamics.

Because an enterprise is **intentionally** created and it is intentionally **designed** the modularity **design** plays an important role. The appropriate modularity of an organisation is dependent on the overall goal of a system. To split up a complex system it is best to look for points of natural division (Baldwin & Clark, 2000), diving “the Idea... at the joints, as nature directs,

not breaking any limb in half as bad carver might.”¹ The needed evolvability of a system is dependent on the purpose of an organization (Dietz et al., 2013). See also:

“If an organisation is **purposeful**, and it is **intentionally designed** then the **organisation design** plays an important role, else there is no intention and no purpose” (Daft et al., 2010).

In many settings, “the real issue is normally not to be modular but how to be modular” (Langlois, 2002). A good modular architecture breaks apart a complex system without destroying it (Baldwin & Clark, 2000). In literature different approaches exist how to break apart a complex system without destroying it.

The definition of a module in a modular system can be defined by *abstraction*, *information hiding* and *interface*:

“A complex system can be managed by dividing it up into smaller pieces and looking at each one separately. When the complexity of one of the elements crosses a certain threshold, that complexity can be isolated by defining a separate abstraction that has a simple interface. The abstraction hides the complexity of the element; the interface indicates how the element interacts with the larger system.” (Baldwin & Clark, 2000)

Definition of architecture:

The architecture of a system is the description of the systems in its components, the relationship between the components and the principles that govern their evolution (IEEE)

2.3.3 Normalized Systems Theory

The Normalized Systems (NS) Theory originates from the field of software development (Mannaert et al., 2016). In software development, it is common practice to incorporate modularity into the design and architecture of software to reduce complexity and increase evolvability (Martin et al., 2018). While modularity is typically achieved through the principles of "high cohesion and low coupling," there is no consensus on the best approach to accomplish this.

Normalized Systems provides design rules to achieve "high cohesion and low coupling," resulting in systems without ripple effects or combinatorial effects. Ripple effects occur when a small change in one part of a system leads to changes in other parts of the system. Combinatorial effects are similar to ripple effects, but their impact on other parts of the system increases with the size of the system as a whole, leading to instability (see Figure 2-5). More detailed explanations are described in paragraph 2.3.3.1.

¹ Plato, *Phaedrus*, 265D: This is the epigraph of Christopher Alexander’s classic work on design theory, *Notes on the Synthesis of Form* (Alexander 21964).

AMS

Figure 2-5 Unstable system (Haerens, 2021)

A stable system has the necessary conditions to remain stable when design changes are made. Stability is defined as Bounded Input results in Bounded Output (BIBO). This results in a modular system with no combinatorial effects, allowing the system to evolve over time.

A stable system has the necessary conditions which a stable modular system must meet to stay stable when design changes must be made. Stability is defined as Bounded Input results in Bounded Output (BIBO). This results in a modular system with no combinatorial effects which results in a system that can evolve over time.

Although NS was developed for software development, providing a foundation for evolvable software, this theory is applicable to various other domains where evolvability and stability are important. NS has been applied in outsourcing (Benazeer et al., 2024), supply chain management (Istanbouli, 2024), firewalls (Haerens, 2021), document management (Oorts et al., 2017) and process modelling (van Nuffel, 2011). NS theory has become a general theory for evolvable design.

In this thesis, NS will be used in the field of innovative IT partnership. This makes it possible for the relationship to evolve over time as conditions change, while maintaining its effectiveness.

2.3.3.1 Ripple effects and combinatorial effects

From systems theory, the stability of a system refers to the situation where a bounded input results in a bounded output. This implies that there should be no change propagation effects in the system. These changes are called ripple effects or combinatorial effects and the lack of these effects are an essential characteristic of a stable system (Mannaert et al., 2011). When a specific change is applied to a partnership, this should require the same effort, irrespective of the size of the partnership or the point in time when the change is applied (Mannaert et al., 2016).

Applying Normalized Systems (NS) theory helps prevent ripple effects or combinatorial effects by avoiding the combination of multiple concerns. This isolation of change drivers

enhances the system's evolvability, making it easier to adapt to new requirements or changing circumstances. One effective way to identify these concerns is by examining the change drivers within a system.

2.3.3.2 Theorems

Normalized Systems Theory contains of four theorems to design evolvable systems. By applying these principles ripple effects will be prevented.

- Separation on Concerns (SoC)
- Separation of State (SoS)
- Action Version Transparency (AVT)
- Data Version Transparency (DVT)

In the context of Innovative IT Partnership, the following theorems are applicable:

Separation of Concerns (SoC)

A processing function can only contain a single task in order to achieve stability (Dietz & Mulder, 2024, p. 274)

Determine from which change driver modularity can be improved. When SoC is not possible, aspects have impact on each other.

Separation of State (SoS)

Calling a processing function within another processing function, needs to exhibit state keeping in order to achieve stability (Dietz & Mulder, 2024, p. 284)

Separation of State can also be considered as Separation of Concerns over time.

Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC)

In addition to the four NS theorems mentioned earlier in this paragraph, there is a special case of Separation of concerns, which is called Cross-Cutting Concerns. It is a concern that is present *cut across* the functional structure (Mannaert et al., 2022).

2.3.4 Exaptation

This thesis explores the concept of exaptation by investigating the applicability of Normalized Systems Theory (NST) to innovative IT partnerships. Originally developed to enhance the modularity and evolvability of software systems, NST is examined here as a potential solution for addressing the complex challenges inherent in innovative IT partnerships. Through this cross-domain application, the research seeks to uncover new perspectives and insights into the construction of innovative IT partnerships, both from an architectural point of view as well as a managerial pint of view.

Figure 2-6 Solution and Application Domain Matrix (Gregor & Hevner, 2013)

2.4 Function of a partnership

2.4.1 Transactional collaboration

Derksen (2013) defines IT outsourcing as “a process whereby an organisation decides to contract out or to sell the firm’s IT assets, people and/or activities to a third party supplier, who in exchange provides and possibly manages these assets, people and/or activities for a fee over an agreed period of time. Using this definition the focus on third party services is emphasized, in which outsourcing is based upon contracting third parties for assets, people, processes and / or activities. The third party provides assets, people and/or activities, but might be managed by the firm.”

This definition contains many forms of IT Outsourcing. Derksen 2013 continues to describe several dimensions that are possible to give some more details. The first one is the delivery model that

1. Offshore outsourcing: Services are provided in a distant foreign country, with a different culture and time zone.
2. Nearshore outsourcing: Services are provided in a nearby foreign country, with a similar culture and time zone.
3. Onshore outsourcing: Services are provided in the same country.
4. Cloud: Services are provided over internet by cloud service providers.

Another way to give more insights is via the type of product or service that is outsourced. (Smuts, 2010) makes the following distinction:

1. Infrastructure: Outsourcing of IT infrastructure management, including servers, networks, and storage technical support
2. Software development and maintenance: Outsourcing the development, testing, and maintenance of software applications across the entire software development lifecycle.

3. Managed services: Outsourcing of managing, monitoring, and maintaining specific IT functions or systems including business process outsourcing.

2.4.1.1 Main drivers for outsourcing

Many different reasons are given for starting IT/IS outsourcing:

Competitive advantage (Benazeer et al. 2020), also Maintain or increase flexibility, benefit from vendors' economies of scale, specialization in core business activities or competences, free resources to other internal services/tasks, sharing of risks of technical complexity and benefits, access to technical expertise, obtain resources not available internally, transfer a function difficult to manage, avoid technological obsolescence, improve IS management (Huysmans et al., 2014, p. 51; Tiwana & Bush, 2007; Varajão et al., 2017)

2.4.1.2 Partnership maturity curve

The type of IT Outsourcing relationship can fluctuate over time depending on changes in the external environment as well as requirements from the client. This corresponds to the maturity of partnerships according to Mehta & Mehta (2010). While the initial stage of maturity emphasizes cost reduction and low client-vendor partnership, the subsequent stage focuses on a moderate client-vendor partnership by becoming more strategically motivated with a better client-vendor fit while in the third stage there is a high client-vendor partnership focussing on relations as the main motivating factor and a good client-vendor fit as indicated in figure 2-6 below.

Figure 2-7 Partnership maturity curve (Mehta & Mehta, 2010)

2.4.1.3 FORT Framework

Kishore et al. (2003) defined different types of relationships by looking at (substitution by) Service Providers and (the strategic impact of) the outsourced ITS Portfolio. This means that the following categories of outsourcing relationships are applicable: (1) Support, (2) alignment, (3) reliance, and (4) alliance, a partnership in which trust is high and contractual

control is low. Outsourcing partnership is a kind of an alliance relationship that goes beyond contract (Kishore et al., 2003).

Figure 2-8 FORT (Four Outsourcing Relationship Types) framework (Kishore et al., 2003)

2.4.1.4 Innovation Paradox in IT Outsourcing

Contracts are rooted in contract law with strong focus on transactional and legal protections (e.g. changes in pricing, service levels, limitation of liability indemnification and liquidated damages). Transactional partnerships are too limited for innovative collaboration due to too much focus on legal aspect i.e. risk reduction which is incompatible with the inherent unpredictability of innovation.

The Innovation in IT Outsourcing paradox is mentioned by (Aubert et al., 2015) because there is an inherent tension in IT Outsourcing where the contract focuses on clear and concise agreements to maintain control while at the same time, there should be room for flexibility and profit and risk sharing to allow for innovation to occur. Four mechanisms that impact this paradox are listed in figure 3-1 below. To counter these, the following self-correcting cycles are described: (1) dual formal reviews, (2) matching governance with level of innovation focus, (3) dynamic decision-making/extreme contracting, and (4) ambidextrous organization (Aubert et al., 2015)

Figure 2-9 Mapping the Reinforcing Cycles (Aubert et al., 2015)

The theory mentioned above is applied by (Kranz, 2021). The results demonstrate that positively framed contracting mechanisms can consider the long-term intention to allow for innovation to happen and thus prevent for example a focus on the short-term benefits.

The success of IT Outsourcing is defined as the degree to which outsourcing reasons of clients are achieved and the level to which in-house problems of concern are solved (Uçar & Bilgen, 2013). However, several studies indicate the following failure aspects in IT Outsourcing: Resistance to internal change, increased management effort, loss of control in fundamental processes for the business, loss of control on the IT management/strategy, Loss of intellectual capital, loss of competencies and skills in information systems, decrease of service quality, loss of flexibility to attend new feeds, unexpected costs, conflict of interest between client and supplier, lack of business knowledge about the business by the supplier, leakage of security about confidential information and business data, to stay tied to suppliers in a dynamic market, exposition to the supplier's risks of instability, dependence on the supplier and threat of opportunism. (Varajão et al., 2017, p. 1055; Verner & Abdullah, 2012)

There has been a shift to become more outsourcing driven where the demand-answer relationship changes into a collaborative way of working on certain activities. This new way of working to become more strategic (thanks to increased trust and collaboration) is however hampered by the rigid contract and service level agreement (SLA) that was originally set up to control the scope and costs (Kranz 2021).

2.4.2 Innovative partnerships definition

An innovative partnership goes beyond a transactional partnership and can be defined as:

A tailored business relationship between two or more organisations working together as partners. This partnership is based upon mutual trust, openness, shared risks and shared

benefits that give a competitive advantage, resulting in business performance greater than would be achieved by the firms individually (Jia & Lamming, 2013) Lambert et al. (1996) and (Ali & Khan, 2014)). The most mature form of this kind of partnership is called vested because the parties have a vested interest in each other's success (Gambal et al., 2022).

2.4.2.1 Quality attributes of an innovative partnership

Quality attributes are prerequisites for a successful IT innovative partnership. These quality attributes are important for the design of a construction that is fit for purpose to allow a successful implementation of the operation. The table below gives an overview of quality attributes applicable to an innovative partnership.

Quality Attribute	Description	Source
Strategic alignment of objectives and capabilities of innovative partnership.	Client and vendor's capabilities must be complementary.	(Mehta & Mehta, 2010) (Søderberg et al., 2013)
Shared risks and Mutual benefits via mutual dependency	Co-creation of value	(Lee & Kim, 2005)
Relational resources are pooled.	Sharing and exchange of knowledge.	(Popoli, 2017) (Lee & Kim, 2005)
Collaborative and innovation driven	Via focus on enhanced service benefits and customer satisfaction,	(Sloniec, 2021)
Commitment and trust	Perceived commitment and trust are essential elements that contribute to the success of outsourcing relationships	(Ates, 2013) (Lane & Lum, 2011) (Sutthiparinyanon & Villegas Puyod, 2022)

Table 2-2 Overview quality attributes in an innovative partnership

2.4.2.2 Partnership contract lifecycle

The research landscape is skewed towards the first two phases (Antecedents and Arrangements), while research on the Generation and Outcomes phases is limited. (Gambal et al., 2022). In this thesis we focus on the arrangement phase and the generation phase. In the arrangement phase, the outsourcing configuration and contract design are created which are linked with the strategic innovation and the collaboration aspect. In the generation phase, there is a need for supporting architectural structures where the modularity aspect comes into place.

Figure 2-10 Strategic innovation through outsourcing: integrative framework (Gambal et al., 2022)

2.4.3 Comparing : Traditional collaboration versus Innovative Partnership

In the evolving landscape of information technology, the nature of inter-organizational collaboration has undergone significant transformation. Traditional collaboration models, often characterized by transactional relationships and clearly defined roles, are increasingly being challenged by the need for more dynamic, innovation-driven partnerships. This section contrasts traditional collaboration with innovative partnerships, highlighting key differences in structure, objectives, and operational dynamics. Understanding these distinctions is essential for organizations seeking to navigate complex, fast-changing environments where adaptability and co-creation are critical to sustained success.

Characteristics	Transactional collaboration	Innovative Partnership	Source
Business Model	Transaction based HOW, focus on tasks. E.g. Statement of Work (SOW)	mutually defined Outcome based WHAT, focus on (common) business value. E.g. Statement of Objectives (SOO),	(Lee & Kim, 2005)
Governance structure	Oversight and focus on counting transactions	Insight to enable collaboration and flexibility.	(Oshri et al., 2015)
Shared value	Lacking, one partner's gain at the expense of the other partner	Partners invested in each other's success and mutually defined outcomes	(Paolo Popoli, 2017) (Espino-Rodríguez &

			Ramírez-Fierro, 2018)
Interdependency	Not encouraged, easy exit	Intentional, long-term, motivated to work together	(Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)
Flexibility	Not easily adaptable to change	Designed to be adaptable to changing business needs	(Lamminmaki, 2011)
Mindset	Win-lose (what's in it for me)	Win-win (what's in it for we)	(Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)
Relationship	Transactions based, focus on cost reduction	Vested Outsourcing /Relational economics for all partners involved	(Søderberg & Romani, 2017) (Kocot & Kocot, 2020)
Knowledge Sharing	Limited knowledge sharing	Sharing and exchange of knowledge between partners thanks to relational resources	(Paolo Popoli, 2017)
Risk Management	Risk reduced in contract	Risk management as inherent part of innovation which is by definition unpredictable	(Alexandrova, 2015)

Table 2-3 Characteristics of transactional collaboration versus innovative partnerships

2.5 Construction of a partnership (white-box)

In the research domain of Enterprise Engineering, several approaches to designing enterprises exist. One of these approaches is DEMO (Dietz & Mulder, 2024) which provides a method to represent the essential aspects of an organization, transactions, in a concise model. This method is based on theoretical underpinning. DEMO provides a means to model the construction of an enterprise (white box) rather than the functionalities (black box).

2.5.1 Construction of a partnership

The evolvability of a partnership is dependent on the components that were used and the relationships between these components. To analyse this the function-construction theory or TAO (Teleology, Affordances and Ontology) theory is used (Dietz & Mulder, 2024). This theory posits that every function is realized by its construction. The intended outcomes and purpose of a partnership (its functions) can only be achieved through its specific structure and components (its construction). Understanding the construction is essential to understanding how the partnership can fulfil its intended functions.

According to the TAO theory the function of a partnership is subjective. Different individuals may perceive or prioritize different functions. In contrast, focusing on the objective construction provides a more stable and shared understanding of what the partnership is. This separation allowed for more effective design, management, and adaptation of the partnership in response to the evolving needs and contexts of its stakeholders.

The construction is brought into being using available technology. The construction is fully abstracted from the realisation and implementation. The focus of this research is the construction of partnership resulting in a white-box model.

A conceptual model of a partnership is needed to define these components. In this case the construction and **operation** of a partnership is relevant (white-box model) and not the possible functions and **behaviour** (black-box model) (Dietz & Mulder, 2024, p. 174). The behaviour of a system is brought about by the operation of the construction. The construction is determined by several construction elements and the relationships between them.

When the construction of a partnership is understood, the partnership can be implemented. This includes the design of the organisation, processes and agreements in the contracts of the partnership. A partnership can be implemented in many ways which is out of-scope of this research.

Figure 2-11 Function - Construction - Implementation (Dietz & Mulder, 2024)

This research will focus exclusively on the construction of a partnership. The construction defines how the partnership can operate, facilitating its interactions with various elements and its environment. These interactions, enabled by the structural relationships, are what drive the partnership's activities. The construction determines the mechanism that makes the partnership successful. This mechanism ultimately leads to the system's desired behaviour and fulfils its function.

By comprehending the structural components of a partnership, it is possible to create a modular design based on Normalised Systems theory. This approach enables the partnership's structure to more effectively absorb changes, thereby minimizing or even eliminating ripple effects.

2.5.2 Elements of construction

To the best of our ability, we were unable to find a comprehensive work or overview in the literature that offers an academic analysis of the construction elements of a partnership.

To create a construction model of a partnership fundamental components found in literature are used. These components are then mapped to DEMO's structural elements (Dietz & Mulder, 2024) to develop a motivated construction model.

A partnership is fundamentally formed by the construction elements described in the table below. The DEMO model contains of the Organisation orientations O-, I-, D-, and M-Organisation (see Figure 2-12). The O-organisation (Original) contains transactions performed by actors which are committed to execute production acts that result in original

new facts. These acts, such as devising, deciding, judging, manufacturing, transporting and observing, fundamentally change the state of the production world and are considered the core business. The I-organisation (Informational) contains transactions performed by actors which are committed to production acts like remembering, computing, deriving facts and sharing facts. This layer supports the O-organisation by providing informational services. The D-organisation (Documental) includes transactions performed by actors which are committed to execute production acts related to the saving, providing, and transforming of documents or data containing facts. This layer supports the I-organisation by providing documental services and can potentially be fully automated. The last organisation is the M-organisation (Material) responsible for the production acts related to they physical carriers of documents or data, known as files, including storing, retrieving, copying, transmitting and destroying. This layer supports the D-organisation by providing material services (Dietz & Mulder, 2024).

The focus of this thesis is on the O-organisation because this organisation represents the part of the partnership that brings about its core business. Understanding the construction and operation of this layer means understanding the essence of what the partnership is about. The other organisations are all needed to support the O-organisation but are not part of it.

According to Dipten & Mulder (2011), every system consists of both a Function and a Construction system type. In this context, we focus solely on the construction elements, as they represent the objective internal structure of the partnership responsible for achieving the partnership's function, including its goals and objectives.

Partnership construction element	DEMO construction elements	Comment
Partners + role; Partners agree to collaborate for a shared goal or objectives (Gambal et al., 2022; Kishore et al., 2003; Lane & Lum, 2011; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).	Transactor role.	Partners provide actors/subjects which will execute the transactor role.
Contract; define the roles, responsibilities, obligations, and rights of each partner, as well as the goals and operational procedures of the partnership (Lane & Lum, 2011; Sun & Lo, 2014; Vitasek et al., 2013).	Part of transactor role.	Acts of devising, deciding, agreeing to performed by a transactor role. The result of these acts are stored in a fact bank. This process will continue when changes are made during the lifetime of the partnership in the contract.
Strategy – proxy via Shared goal and objectives (Kranz, 2021; McNamara et al., 2020; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).	Part of transactor roles.	Agreement on Shared goals and objectives is the result of devising/deciding acts by the transactor roles.
Finance – Shared benefits or risk; shared benefits and risks within the partnership (Lane & Lum, 2011).	Part of transactor roles.	Agreement regarding shared goals and objectives are the result of devising/deciding acts by the transactor role.
Finance – Funding; shared funding by the partners of a partnership (Hofman et al., 2017; Vitasek et al., 2013).	Part of transactor roles.	Agreements regarding shared goals and objectives are part of the transaction and commitments.
Capabilities and knowledge; Capabilities and knowledge are contributed by partners and shared for the partnership’s shared goals or	Part of the construction of O-, I-, D-, and M-organization.	Every system type contains different types of capabilities and knowledge.

objectives (Gambal et al., 2022; Kranz, 2021; Ven et al., 2010).		
Organization; Organization is the operational architecture of a partnership (Tee et al., 2019).	Transaction tree by multiple transactor roles.	-
Innovation	Result of a transaction	-

Table 2-4 Partnership construction elements related to DEMO construction elements (Dietz & Mulder, 2024)

Presented below is a summary of the partnership construction elements mapped onto the system orientation construction, along with the organization types (O-, I-, D-, and M-organisation).

Figure 2-12 Organisation types and System orientations (Dipten and Mulder 2019)

Based on the construction elements, supported by DEMO, a new construction model for partnerships is proposed. This model is composed of elements derived from the construction system orientation and the O-system type.

Figure 2-13 Construction elements of a partnership (own work)

3 Research Design and Approach

This chapter outlines the methodological approach, which is design science research, combining practical relevance with academic rigor. It includes the creation of an expert panel followed by in-depth interviews with four experts on mitigating or cultivating the impact of change drivers of modularity on innovative IT partnerships.

3.1 Methodology

Figure 3-1 Based on Design Science (Gregor & Hevner, 2013)

We apply design science research approach. On the one hand, we have the theories to support the research approach in a rigorous methodology. On the other hand, there are relevant challenges in the practice to better understand the change drivers, the construction of and the quality attributes of innovative IT partnerships.

3.2 Research design

3.2.1 Research Scope

Figure 3-2 Research design scope

To explore the impact of modularity on innovative IT partnerships the following topics are in scope:

- An artefact for a change driver will be developed to investigate the impact of modularity (step A).
- The artefact will focus on the construction of an innovative partnership (step B).

The following topics are out of scope for this research:

- The function and implementation of a partnership are out of scope for this research (step B).
- The output of an innovative partnership is an innovation. This step is also out of scope for this research (step C).

3.2.2 Research Approach

The research process consists of three steps. The first step is to collect the relevant change drivers by enquiring within the expert panel. The second step is to develop an artefact for a change driver. Subsequently the artefact is prefilled to ensure a consistent starting point for each expert discussion with the individual expert. In the third step the pre-filled artefact is discussed with the expert and subsequently updated in an iterative way.

Figure 3-3 Research process steps

3.3 Step 1: Panel discussion

3.3.1 Panel Preparation

The authors selected 10 experts for the panel which were selected based upon the following inclusion criteria:

- Minimum 10 years of working experience in contributing to innovative IT partnerships
- Has a role as director, leader or manager with decision making mandate
- From various industries to allow views from different angles and thus reduce bias
- Personal/Professional network from the authors, enriched with network from the professors
- Company must be based in Belgium or in the Netherlands

The authors contacted the experts personally and obtained 10 positive answers to join the two hours panel discussion on 5th February 2025. The timing was from 17h00 to 19h00 so after working hours to allow all experts to join the panel.

Various tools were planned to allow capturing the data provided. MS Teams to have automatic transcription of the interviews to have a verbal overview of the discussions (consent was obtained verbally from all participants in the panel). These results were cross-referenced with the feedback given in the supporting meetinwizard.nl tool (see below). We also used the meetingwizard.nl tool to facilitate the usage of GSS (Bostrom et al., 1993).

Before performing the panel discussion, a dry-run of the meeting wizard was done with the professor to make sure that the facilitators were fully prepared up-front. After the dry-run we did some adjustments in the meetingwizard.nl tool and we also applied that setting to a dry-run with one expert to make sure that the objectives and questions were easy and clear to understand. This resulted in some further enrichments to further clarify. Note that this expert also joined the panel discussion which could be seen as potential bias, even if we did not discuss the content in-depth during the preparatory session.

3.3.2 Panel discussion / Collecting the experts' opinions

The authors facilitated the panel discussion with the various participants and included all experts in the discussion. The benefits of this way of working allows to capture input from all participants, both in data scoring using the Likert scale from 1 till 5 and comments on why this score was given. In addition, the answers given indicated that the experts had different interpretations on various concepts which led to enriching discussions that shed more light on the various interpretations. This information will be used in the analysis after the panel discussion.

3.4 Step 2: Proposed artefact

The aim of this step is to create a structured artefact for each of the three selected change drivers. We created an artefact template that we prefilled with a proposal for the expected results. The reason to prefill this is to ensure consistency across the four expert interviews by providing a common starting point. The objective of this step is to have a proposed change driver artefact that combines literature findings and input from the expert panel and enriched with initial interpretations by the authors. This proposed artefact is input for the evaluation by the experts, see the next paragraph Step 3: Evaluation artefact .

Figure 3-4 Elements of change driver artefact model

Every artefact is based on a changer driver and a proposal of the artefacts is made by the authors taking to allow for the same starting point with each individual expert. For a selection of the artefacts, these are discussed in-depth with the individual expert interviews with the aim to enrich and validate these selected change driver artefacts. Below you will find a more detailed description of the steps one to four.

Figure 3-5 Artefact template

3.4.1.1 Building Block 1 Change drivers of partnerships

Change drivers for partnerships were not found in literature so an expert panel will be used to collect relevant change drivers for partnerships. Change drivers are described in paragraph 4.1.1 and were collected by means of an expert panel described in paragraph 3.3.2.

Change drivers are used to validate the applicability of modularity in partnerships.

3.4.1.2 Building Block 2 Modular representation of partnership

To investigate modularity by experts a modular construction was needed. Every artefact used all relevant construction elements of the partnership construction model which is described in paragraph 2.5.1. This building block is proposed by the authors and has been validated on the following aspects:

1. Proposed construction elements related to the specific artefact. This aspect is related to Research Question 2.
2. Structure in which the construction elements are organized. This aspect is related to measures implemented to adhere to NST in managing change. This aspect is related to Research Question 3.

This building block is used to validate the construction model of a partnership, addressing Research Question 2.

3.4.1.3 Building Block 3 Modularity

This building block explores the impact of modularity on a partnership. The first part describes relevant theories of Normalized Systems Theory for the related change driver. Normalized Systems theories were described in paragraph 2.3.3.

The second section details the measures implemented to adhere to NST in managing change as outlined by the change driver. Both provides insights into whether modularity, by means of NST, can be applied to the construction of partnerships. Together with Building Block 4 this will give an answer on Research Question 3.

3.4.1.4 Building Block 4 Quality attributes & Management Measures

This part explores the impact of the change driver on the quality attributes of a partnership. The first part describes quality attributes (see paragraph 2.4.2.1) that are significantly impact by the change driver of the artefact. The second part examines the measures to either mitigate or cultivate the impact of the change driver on the relevant quality attributes.

Together with Building Block 3 this will give an answer on Research Question 3.

3.5 Step 3: Evaluation artefact

The objective of this step is to validate and enrich the proposed artefact as described in the paragraph Step 2: Proposed artefact. The authors conduct four individual expert interviews to present, discuss and refine the artefact. We incorporated the gained insights and practical perspectives, while also considering the results from the literature study. The resulting output is a validated and enriched change driver artefact, incorporating expert input, which will be used to address Research Questions 2 and 3.

4 Research Results

This chapter provides an overview of the change drivers identified by the expert panel. The results indicate several change drivers with high variability, meaning definitions and impacts vary significantly among experts. We selected the three change drivers with the highest variability and discussed them in-depth with four experts, resulting in various mitigating and cultivating measures.

4.1 Step 1: Experts Panel Results

We asked the following questions to the ten experts in the panel. We did the exercise online via MS Teams to show the accompanying presentation with a short introduction as well as the questions. In addition, we used the meetingwizard.nl tool as the Group Support System to capture the complete input from all participating experts to allow further analysis after this panel session.

Below an overview of the background of the experts we selected for the Expert Panel.

Expert	Industry	Country	Level	Experience (Years)	Business	IT
1	IT	The Netherlands	General Director	29	Yes	Yes
2	Manufacturing	The Netherlands	Strategic Account Manager	36	Yes	No
3	Manufacturing	The Netherlands	Chief Technology Officer	36	No	Yes
4	Maritime	The Netherlands	Vendor Manager	27	Yes	Yes
5	Maritime	The Netherlands	Innovation Manager	26	Yes	Yes
6	Banking	Belgium	Enterprise Architect	24	No	Yes
7	IT	Belgium	Chief Technology Officer	20	No	Yes
8	Contracting	Belgium	Product Manager	15	Yes	Yes
9	Publishing	Belgium	Partner Manager	11	Yes	Yes
10	IT	Belgium	Sales Manager	32	Yes	Yes

Table 4-1 Background Experts in the Panel

4.1.1 Change drivers

The first question to the panel was ‘which change drivers can you identify in your practice?’ to have an initial collection of these change drivers in random order. We applied an open question to not influence the experts with our literature research.

This led to the following initial collection of change drivers (in random order):

Change driver
Aging workforce
Availability of resources
Availability of subsidies (external)
Capabilities within a partner
Change in leadership
Change in management
Change in strategy

Change of ownership (of parts) of company
Cultural and organizational shifts
Deliver new types of products & services
Disruption by competitors
Events that change level of Trust (internal)
Fast pace of technology evolution
Geopolitical changes
Geotechnical
Increasing complexity
Leaving capabilities
New distribution channels
Opportunity to work with disruptive actors (perceived as such)
Pandemics
Political changes
Product development
Regulation
Rising costs
Technology

Table 4-2 Initial collection change drivers

An important observation from the experts was that there needs to be a clear and concise definition of these change drivers to avoid different interpretations.

We consolidated the changed drivers based upon the experts' feedback (in random order).

Change driver
Geopolitical/Political Changes: (Includes Geopolitical changes, Political changes)
Technological Advancements/Disruption: (Includes Fast pace of technology evolution, Technology disruption by competitors)
Economic Factors: Includes Availability of Subsidies
Rising costs
Availability of resources
Strategic Shifts: (Includes Change in strategy, Deliver new types of products & services, Product development)
Organizational Dynamics: Includes Capabilities within a partner, Leaving capabilities, Aging workforce
Change in management, Cultural and organizational shifts
Change of ownership
Change in Leadership
Regulatory Changes: (Includes Regulation)
Trust Fluctuations: (Includes Events that changes level of Trust) (internal and external)
Emerging Opportunities/Disruptive Actors: (Includes Opportunity to work with disruptive actors)
External Shocks/Crises: (Includes Pandemics)
Market/Distribution Changes: (Includes New distribution channels)
Complexity: (Includes Increasing complexity)

Table 4-3 Consolidated collection of change drivers

4.1.2 Consolidated change drivers

For the second question, we asked the experts to rate the consolidated change drivers on a Likert scale of 1 to 5 with 1 being negative impact, 3 neutral and 5 positive impact. We asked the experts to apply their latest initiative they were involved with to apply these ratings.

During the GSS, we learned that the impact of some change drivers could be seen as both negative and positive, depending on one’s personal experience. This was clarified during the GSS panel session and was also verified after the session. Feedback from the experts on the panel discussion was positive and the authors could contact them afterwards in case clarifications were needed.

After the session, the authors analysed the comments with the scores given to assure consistency as there was some unclarity identified during the panel session. For four people, there was unclarity and thus the authors contacted these experts after the session. These four experts either confirmed having the same understanding (i.e. no need for change to the results) or an updated rating list was provided. This was subsequently updated in the overall average score of change driver by the panel to allow proper comparison of the data.

The sorting of these change factors is done with the highest variability on top. The reason for this is that these change factors indicating the most diverging experts’ views on top of the list of change drivers in Table 4-4 Change drivers ordered by variability.

Change driver	Rating	Variability
Strategic Shifts: (Includes Change in strategy, Deliver new types of products & services, Product development)	2,6	72%
Regulatory Changes: (Includes Regulation)	3,3	68%
Organizational Dynamics: Includes Capabilities within a partner, Leaving capabilities, Aging workforce	2,3	65%
Geopolitical/Political Changes: (Includes Geopolitical changes, Political changes)	2,9	62%
Availability of resources	2,6	61%
Change in Leadership	2,7	56%
Change in management, Cultural and organizational shifts,	2,6	55%
Technological Advancements/Disruption: (Includes Fast pace of technology evolution, Technology disruption by competitors)	2,9	51%
Rising costs	2,7	49%
Emerging Opportunities/Disruptive Actors: (Includes Opportunity to work with disruptive actors)	2,5	47%
Market/Distribution Changes: (Includes New distribution channels)	2,7	39%
Complexity: (Includes Increasing complexity)	3,6	36%
Economic Factors: Includes Availability of Subsidies	2,7	36%
Trust Fluctuations: (Includes Events that changes level of Trust) (internal and external)	1,8	34%
External Shocks/Crises: (Includes Pandemics)	3,1	34%
Change of ownership	2,0	31%

Table 4-4 Change drivers ordered by variability

4.1.3 Impact of change drivers

The experts mentioned the following comments with a positive or negative impact on the innovative partnership in table 4-4 below. Most of the strategic shift are perceived to have a

negative impact on the innovative partnership. This means that there is a need for identifying mitigating measures proactively when these change drivers occur. In addition, a limited number of change drivers can also have a positive impact on the innovative partnership where disruption can also lead to additional innovation.

Change Driver	Positive impact on innovative partnership	Negative impact on innovative partnership
Strategic shifts	Not mentioned	Partnership under pressure with risk of termination of partnership
Regulatory changes	More awareness leading to increase in clients for partnership. Driver of innovation	Regulation at start impact as solution no longer covers (fully) the regulation
Organizational dynamics	Not mentioned	Impact on changing capabilities needs to be mitigated. Lack of identification of new opportunities
Geopolitical changes	Exceptionally positive e.g. compensation certain resources	Unpredictable and therefore negative impact on partnership
Availability of resources	Not mentioned	Mostly negative in case of scarce resources
Change in leadership	Not mentioned	Considered mostly negative in practice as partnership is re-assessed by all partners and possible change in vision impact.
Change in management	Partnership that was 'stuck' can get new energy because of new management	Change in Decision Making Unit is considered always a challenge, even if only indirect.
Technological advancements / disruption	Considered positive impact for partnership	Clients may choose competitors in case of disruption. Partnership may wait too long to work on innovation
Rising costs	Not mentioned	Change in business model, impact depends on market size
Emerging opportunities	New capabilities added.	More competition. Impact of patents not evident and expensive
Market/distribution changes	For digital products, impact is limited	For non-digital products, impact is significant and may stop innovation
Complexity	Stimulates new ideas and driver of innovative software solutions. Can enforce the relationship e.g. DORA regulation	Negative impact possible when complexity increases
Economic factors incl. subsidies	Subsidies can stimulate innovation but depends on administrative effort need to obtain them.	Less subsidies over time can impact the innovation investment budget

Trust Fluctuations	Not mentioned	Mostly negative but mitigating action is to monitor this and act quickly No trust is no partnership
Change of ownership	If vision is shared, limited impact	can be negative if owners are not very involved

Table 4-5 Change drivers from expert panel

4.1.4 Mitigation and cultivation of impact of change drivers

Finally, we asked the experts to list cultivating factors of the change driver ‘Complexity’ as this change factor has the highest cultivating score (Table 4-4 Change drivers ordered by variability). The experts mentioned the following cultivating measures for Complexity: Have an open communication within the partnership. Identify clear roles and responsibilities within the partnership, create a shared understanding of vision, goals, assumptions and governance.

The results were subsequently consolidated with the aim to strengthen the validation by four experts. Three change drivers were identified with the highest variability to discuss mitigating or cultivating actions with these experts. This high variability indicates that there are different views within the panel of experts and thus these change drivers merit further analysis.

4.2 Step 2: Preparation Artefact

To strengthen the analysis, individual expert interviews were conducted based on the three change drivers that exhibited a clear modular aspect within the partnership construction and with the highest variability in the panel discussion. This variability indicates divergent expert opinions and thus needing more clarity. The three selected change drivers are:

1. Strategic Shift
2. Leaving Partner
3. New Partner

Unlike the earlier panel discussion, the expert sessions were guided by a pre-structured and pre-filled template developed by the authors. This template integrated multiple sections, combining insights from the panel discussions with relevant findings from the literature. The structured format aimed to facilitate focused dialogue and ensure consistency across expert contributions (see Figure 3-4).

4.3 Step 3: Expert sessions – demonstrate artefact

The information in paragraph 4.1 gives an initial overview of change drivers in innovative IT partnerships, their perceived impact as well as potential mitigating and cultivating measures. To fortify these initial results, we also had four individual one-hour interviews with experts in roles of chief executive officer, enterprise architect and sales manager. One of these experts participated also in the panel whereas the other three did not participate previously. Below an overview of the background of the experts we selected for the individual expert interviews.

Expert	Industry	Country	Level	Experience (Years)	Business	IT
1	IT	Belgium	Sales Manager	32	Yes	Yes
2	Banking	Belgium	Enterprise Architect	29	No	Yes
3	Maritime	The Netherlands	Enterprise Architect	42	Yes	Yes
4	Consultancy	Belgium	Chief Executive Officer	34	Yes	Yes

Table 4-6 Background of the experts of the individual interviews

Below a summary of the results of the expert meetings.

4.3.1 Change driver: Strategic shift

4.3.1.1 Change driver description

The change driver is the strategic shift of the partnership or partners as the strategy can change over time.

4.3.1.2 Construction components of partnership

Within the construction of the partnership (see paragraph 2.5), the following components are impacted for this change driver:

1. Shared goals and objectives defined as Strategy.
2. Partners
3. Contract

Figure 4-1 Relevant construction components of a strategic shift

Findings of expert interviews:

1. **Structured discussion of changes:** Changes within partnerships are often not explicitly discussed in a structured manner, highlighting the need for more formalized communication.
2. **Contracts with fixed and flexible elements:** Contracts should include both fixed and flexible elements to support adaptability and manage change, beyond simply minimizing risk. The construction model has not included the distinction between fixed and flexible elements.

3. **Recognizable construction components:** The construction components in the model are easily identifiable and help to make the elements of a partnership explicit, facilitating better understanding and management.

4.3.1.3 *Relevant NS theories*

The following NS theories were applied:

1. **Separation of Concerns (SoC):** Partners are separate concerns and must be autonomous to innovate (Sun & Lo, 2014).
2. **Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC):** The impact of a change in strategy cut across all partners. This creates ripple effects through every partner in the partnership.
3. **Separation of State (SoS):** The partnership's strategy will evolve over time, with each new version representing a distinct state and being stored in a fact bank. This approach reflects the principle of Separation of Concerns over time.

4.3.1.4 *Measures based on NS theories*

This section describes the measures that can be implemented to adhere to NS theories within the context of partnerships.

Implement periodic synchronization meetings to align with shared objectives of the partnership (CCC) and individual objectives of partners (SoC) to prevent unexpected leave. Periodic review synchronization meetings, detailed in the partnership contract, serve as a formal moment in time when changes are formalized of changes in partnership's shared objectives and the individual partner, preventing ripple effects (SoS).

Findings of expert interviews:

1. **Regular sync meetings:** Organize sync meetings every few months to discuss strategic and tactical changes. Usually strategic objectives of partners (SoC) and partnerships (CCC) are not explicitly and frequently discussed. Sync meetings results in decoupling of partners from the strategic shift because they are considered as proxies. These meetings supports the discussion of interest across all partners and partnership which makes it possible to directly steer when changes occur.
2. **Agreements:** Document agreements in an addendum to the contract, providing a reference for previous decisions and supporting partnership evolvability. This will separate different states of the partnership (addendum of a revised contract) and realize decoupling between every new version of the contract (SoS)

4.3.1.5 *Quality attributes*

The relevant quality attributes for innovative partnerships are:

1. **Shared objectives** (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012) (Kranz, 2021)
 - a. Partners actively collaborate which leads to mutual benefits (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012) and strengthening of the partnership.
 - b. Partners are fully aligned with shared objectives (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012). There is a focus on the 'what' to unlock opportunities for innovation and growth that might not be possible in traditional transactional relationships (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

- c. There is a focus on adding value to the partnership.
2. **High interdependency** between partners needed to realize innovation. Due to a lack of knowledge or expertise partners are highly dependent on each other (Ven et al., 2010; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

4.3.1.6 Managerial measures

Partner might leave the partnership unexpectedly when a mismatch develops between the objective of the partner and the partnership. Development of opportunistic behaviour will weaken the partnership (Sun & Lo, 2014).

Findings of expert interviews:

- **Strategic shifts:** Changes in strategy can impact all aspects of the partnership, sometimes requiring a complete restart. Tactical elements must remain adaptable to accommodate shifts. While the overarching strategy remains constant, its implementation may change, affecting all aspects of the partnership and sometimes requiring a complete restart.
- **Recognition and gratitude:** Incorporate recognition and gratitude explicitly into arrangements or contracts to reinforce positive relationships and collaboration during strategic shifts.
- **Role of diverse partners:** Adjusting tactics may necessitate involvement from various types of partners. Major partners benefit from collaboration with smaller, innovative partners to achieve strategic objectives, highlighting the equal significance of each partner in the partnership's success.

4.3.2 Change driver: Leaving partner

4.3.2.1 Change driver description

This change driver concerns the departure of a partner. When partners leave, it may result in changes in the availability of essential capabilities, like knowledge and expertise (Kishore et al., 2003) and shared benefits and risks (Alexandrova, 2015; Lane & Lum, 2011).

4.3.2.2 Construction components of partnership

Within the construction of the partnership (see paragraph 2.5), the following components are impacted for this change driver:

1. Partners
2. Innovation
3. Capabilities (knowledge and expertise)

Figure 4-2 Relevant construction components of leaving partner

Findings of expert interviews:

- **Visualization of risks:** The Partnership construction helps visualize the risks associated with a partner leaving, fostering evolvability to manage ongoing stress, albeit at an extra cost and time investment.
- **Capabilities:**
 - o Two types of capabilities exist. Capabilities needed for the partnership and capabilities belonging to partners.
 - o Distinguish between core and commodity capabilities is essential in partnership construction.

4.3.2.3 Relevant NS theories

The following NS theories were applied:

Separation of Concerns (SoC):

- Capabilities are designed to be independent of one another, simplifying their maintenance and development.
- Essential capabilities rely on multiple partners to enhance continuity and reduce dependency on any single partner.

Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC):

- A leave of a partner can result in the unavailability of a capability impact the full partnership and all partners.

4.3.2.4 Measures based on NS theories

This section describes the measures that can be implemented to adhere to NS theories within the context of partnerships.

Support knowledge sharing and building to create stable and autonomous capabilities (**SoC**). Capabilities should be developed independently to minimize interdependencies, which enhances their maintenance and supports ongoing improvement. Additionally, it's essential to

continuously align the necessary capabilities among partners to ensure the capability's continuity.

Findings of expert interviews:

1. **Capabilities management:**

- Distributed capabilities are crucial for strengthen the partnership. Continuity of shared capabilities is better assured because knowledge is shared across multiple partners.
- While capabilities must be autonomous to be managed in isolation, within a partnership, isolation of capabilities is undesirable as it hinders innovation. Overlap of capabilities promotes innovation and is more important than continuity and stability.
- Avoid duplicating capabilities among partners due to high costs.

2. **Knowledge sharing and governance:** Ensure that each partner has a representative within the capabilities (SoC) of other partners to facilitate knowledge sharing and promote effective governance. Sharing critical capabilities among partners is key to fostering the continuity of these capabilities. However, another expert stated that knowledge sharing is difficult in a partnership because the foundation of a partnership often relies on the absence of expertise of knowledge.

3. **Role of legal in partnerships:** Legal frameworks (=contract) are vital in strengthening partnerships by assessing partner contributions and bridging differences, thereby maintaining a focus on partnership growth rather than solely on minimizing risks.

4. **Guidelines:** Create guidelines, serving as contracts, to flexibly manage situations rather than relying on rigid boundaries. These guidelines accommodate varying circumstances and promote resilience within the partnership.

4.3.2.5 *Quality attributes*

The relevant quality attributes for innovative partnerships are:

1. **Co-creation of value** are essential to foster innovation in partnerships (Sun & Lo, 2014; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012; Kranz, 2021)
2. **Mutually committed** to each others success (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)

4.3.2.6 *Managerial measures*

A change in capabilities could potentially disrupt the continuity of innovative activities (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

Change in shared benefits and risks have impact on all parties involved.

Findings of expert interviews:

- **Expertise hiring:** When a partner leaves, they may seek to hire expertise from remaining partners, impacting partnership dynamics and resource distribution.
- **Maturity levels:** The maturity level of partners can significantly affect the partnership, influencing collaboration effectiveness and adaptability to change.
- **Knowledge sharing vs. capabilities:** Knowledge sharing differs from capabilities but can facilitate their realization. It is crucial for fostering capabilities within the partnership.

- **Grace period and poaching policy:** Define a grace period before a partner can leave and establish policies to prevent poaching between partners.
- **Leaver principles:** Apply the good leaver, bad leaver principle, recognizing that partner departure can be beneficial depending on the context. Clear agreements regarding leaving partners can strengthen commitment.
- **Journey focus:** View the partnership as a journey supported by clear agreements for both positive and challenging times, emphasizing shared goals over capability-driven objectives.

4.3.3 Change driver: New partner

4.3.3.1 Change driver description

The change driver is that a partner can join the partnership (Kranz, 2021). Change in partners might cause changes in the agreements of shared benefits and risks (Alexandrova, 2015; Gambal et al., 2022; Lane & Lum, 2011).

4.3.3.2 Construction components of partnership

Within the construction of the partnership (see paragraph 2.5), the following components are impacted for this change driver:

1. Partners
2. Shared benefits and risks (financial, knowledge/skills, market share)

Figure 4-3 Relevant construction elements of new partner

Every partner is autonomous and all share benefits and risks which may not be evenly distributed.

Findings of expert interviews:

- **Modularity in partnerships:** Applying modularity through NST is recognized for its ability to enhance clarity in partnerships. This approach enables a structured and precise evaluation of partnerships, thereby aiding in the establishment of a stable foundation that remains resilient amidst variability.

- **Interplay between tactics and operations:** The construction model can aid in distinguishing and organizing operations and tactics. Usually the challenge lies in clearly defining these two aspects, as they often overlap.
- **Shared benefits and risks:** A new partner causes changes in benefits & risks and might impacts all partners.

4.3.3.3 *Relevant NS theories*

The following NS theory was applied:

1. **Separation of Concerns (SoC):** Partners are independent organizations and must derive benefits from the partnership.
2. **Cross-Cutting Concern (CCC):** Partners share both benefits and risks and must actively collaborate to strengthen the partnership (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012). Any change in shared benefits and risks impacts all partners.

4.3.3.4 *Measures based on NS theories*

This sections describes the measures that can be implemented to adhere to NS theories within the context of partnerships.

Conduct periodic review and synchronization meetings to align shared benefits and risks among partners (**CCC**) when new partners join the partnership agreement. The allocation of benefits and risks is influenced by various factors, including the type of capability, such as whether it is considered as a commodity or core capability.

Findings of expert interviews:

- **Governance by sync meeting:** Periodic sync meetings are essential to manage ripple effects as a result of changes in shared benefits and risks.
- **Proactive agreements:** Establish agreements regarding the entry of new partners, addressing both success and potential failure scenarios. This proactive approach is often overlooked, but is crucial for managing change effectively when it actually happens.

4.3.3.5 *Quality attributes*

The relevant quality attributes for innovative partnerships are:

1. **Shared benefits** as mutual compensation for every partner and the partnership as a whole (Alexandrova, 2015; Gambal et al., 2022; Lane & Lum, 2011; Vitasek et al., 2013). Continuous and actively growing partnership so all partners can benefit from it in the long run. There is no focus on partner's own benefits, which is limited to short-term benefits.
2. A new partner can bring **new knowledge and experience** which can foster relationship learning. This has a positive effect on joint innovation and transfer ideas (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)

4.3.3.6 *Managerial measures*

A new partnership can introduce uncertainty and potentially lead to increase conflict. This necessitates a re-evaluation of various aspects, including contractual agreements that clearly outline shared risks and benefits (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).

Findings of expert interview:

- **Cost structure and competition:** Introducing a new partner alters the cost structure and competitive dynamics, affecting all partners.
- **Need for continuous alignment:** Continuous alignment and communication are critical for maintaining partnership quality and cohesion.
- **Partner value:** New partners can be pivotal in ensuring partnership success. Value assessments should consider the partnership as a whole rather than focusing on individual entities.
- **Focus on partnership strength:** Prioritize strengthening the partnership over ensuring 'fair' distribution of benefits and risks, as fairness is irrelevant if it doesn't contribute to the overall partnership's robustness.

5 Discussion

This chapter compares the expert findings to the academic literature. It also mentions the limitations of this research, cites the contribution of this research and offers suggestions for future research.

Modularity is a means to perform structured and systematic analysis about modularity aspects of partnerships.

Modularity can be partly applied on the construction model of partnerships.

We applied triangulation by performing a literature study on modularity and innovative partnerships, having an expert panel discussion to collect information from the practice and used the combined input of the literature study with the collective expert findings to discuss this with individual experts using amongst others our proposed construction model as input for this interview.

5.1 Interpretation of findings

5.1.1 RQ1: Relevant Change Drivers

In the expert panel relevant change drivers are collected. The identified change drivers were grouped used as input for this research. The selected change drivers correspond with the Competitive forces model (Porter, 1979) and have the highest variability and modular components.

The selected change drivers are:

- Strategic shift
- Leaving partner
- New partner

5.1.2 RQ2: Construction of innovative partnership

The second research question concerns the construction model of an innovative IT partnership. In paragraph 2.5 the construction components of an innovative partnership was proposed. This model was incrementally validated by four experts for three change drivers. The result of this analysis is further detailed out in Appendix E: Research results - Construction model and shown in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1 Validated construction components

5.1.3 RQ3: Impact modularity on quality attributes of partnership

The results from both architectural and managerial lenses are discussed to assess the impact of modularity on the quality attributes of a partnership. (see Figure 5-2).

Figure 5-2 Discussion of architecture and managerial lens

RQ3: What is the impact of **modularity** on **quality attributes** of an **innovative IT partnership**?

To evaluate the impact of applying modularity by NST on a partnership, two components are compared per change driver: The measures implemented to comply with NST (See 3a/3b in Figure 5-2), and the managerial measures to align with partnership's quality attributes (see 4a/4b in Figure 5-2).

To compare the components the NS theorems are used as a starting point to explore which theorems can be applied on a partnership.

Coherence between 3a/b and 4a/b suggests that modularity can be successfully applied on the construction model of a partnership. Below are the findings that are coherent and contradictory:

Coherent findings: →

Complying to NS theorems, we find the following similarities between the architectural lens and managerial lens. This suggests that modularity could be applied on the construction model of a partnership:

- **Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC):** → **Align partners**

- **Measure: Regular synchronization meetings to align interests between partners (strategic shift, new partner).** Regular synchronization meetings enable partners to frequently align their shared interests (e.g., goals, objectives, benefits, and risks). This approach corresponds with managing mismatches and mitigating opportunistic behaviour related to managerial measures. Sync meetings act as proxies, fostering a proactive approach among partners (SoC) to align their interests. Consequently, there is little need to individually persuade partners to align, resulting in minimal ripple effects. A high alignment of partners corresponds to the quality attribute of “strategic alignment” between all partners (see paragraph 2.4.2.1).
- **Result: Managing Cross-Cutting Concerns**
- **Separation of Concerns (SoC): → Confirm autonomy of partners**
 - **Measure: Regular synchronization meetings to (strategic shift).** Partners always take into account their own interest when joining a partnership. Partners want to stay autonomous, also in an innovative partnership. Regular synchronization meetings helps partners to share their own interest and align with the partnership interests continuously. This mechanism provides the means to partners to be able to pursue their interests independently while still being part of a larger whole. This also strengthen the managerial measure of “managing mismatches and opportunistic behaviour” by continuously align partners with each other, it is possible to discuss everything so that nothing stays under the table. This might prevent opportunistic behaviour.
- **Separation of States (SoS): → realign partners in previous made agreements**
 - **Documenting agreements (strategic shift)** . Agreements made in synchronization meetings are documented in contract to provide a historical reference for previous decisions and acknowledgements and supports partnership evolvability. This approach separates changes in strategic agreements and facilitates a clear transition between contract versions, enhancing decoupling between changes (SoS). Hence, this strengthens the quality attribute “shared objective” and “high interdependency”. By documenting recognition and gratitude making it explicit why partners are dependent of each other and strengthen the “shared objective”.

Contradictory findings → hampers innovation

Examples below:

- **Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC):**
 - **Distributed partnership capabilities (leaving partner).** The departure of a partner may lead to certain capabilities becoming unavailable and impacts the partnership including all partners (CCC). Distributing capabilities across multiple partners enhances continuity and stability. However, according to managerial measures, this approach is often too costly or not possible. The reason to start a partnership is due to a lack of capabilities. Duplication of capabilities across partners is therefore not possible.
- **Separation of Concerns (SoC):**

- **Isolating partnership capabilities (leaving partner).** The development of capabilities needed by the partnership can be more easily achieved in isolation, due to minimal dependencies (**SoC**). However, according to experts' interviews developing capabilities in isolation might impede innovation. Promoting overlapping partnership capabilities is more important than focusing solely on continuity and stability, as it fosters a more innovative environment. This corresponds with the quality attribute of “co-creation of value” whereby partners need to collaborate to make innovation happen.

We have identified several suggestions for the successful application of modularity (NST) in partnerships, such as the need for continuous alignment between partners. However, we also observe some contradictory findings, for example the distribution of capabilities within the partnership. These findings will be elaborated in paragraph 5.1.4.

5.1.4 Implications – The art of balancing autonomy and collaboration

The following implications are found in this research.

First implication: NST theorems hinder innovation.

Normalized Systems Theory typically minimizes ripple and combinatorial effects, promoting evolvability and fostering innovation. However, the resulting independence can hinder innovation by creating barriers that prevent partners from collaborating effectively and innovating together.

Second implication: Aligning tensions between partners and partnership interest.

The role of Normalized Systems Theory shifts from primarily preventing ripple effects, which are conditions for innovation, to aligning individual partners' interests with the partnership's defined goals and objectives. The Cross-Cutting Concerns (**CCC**) theorem manages ripple effects arising from change drivers that create imbalances in shared interests, such as goals, objectives, benefits, and risks. These imbalances affect all partners and can weaken the partnership if alignment diminishes due to a lack of recognition or gratitude. Individual partners' interests, managed by Separation of Concerns (**SoC**), are crucial to acknowledge and can be discussed during synchronization meetings, which aim to align shared interests. The Separation of State (**SoS**) theorem is vital for documenting shared interests over time, ensuring that evolving interests, due to identified change drivers causing imbalances, are effectively addressed. All theorems work together (see Figure 5-3) to align partners, reinforce shared interests, and strengthen the partnership.

Figure 5-3 Application NST on a partnership

General findings

The used artefact and construction model is supportive in making partnership development stronger in a structured way by systematically managing the polarity (interests of partners vs partnership).

To summarize: The role of Normalized Systems Theory in achieving an evolvable partnership construction appears limited. However, its strategic role in aligning individual partners with the partnership's objectives and goals is notably strong.

5.2 Contributions

This research adds to both science and practice as described in next two paragraphs.

5.2.1 Contribution to science

- Exaptation: We applied NS theory from software development on a new domain i.e. innovative IT partnerships.
- Multi-faceted research: We used two lenses for this research, namely architecture and management lens resulting in multi-faceted research.
- Construction model: By applying modularity, by means of a conceptual construction model, a foundation has been developed to systematically analyse and improve the design of partnerships and foster evolvable constructions. This includes applying DEMO to develop a construction model of a partnership.
- Collection change drivers: We created an initial collection of change drivers from experts in the field using a panel discussion.
- Measures: Initial insights into mitigating and cultivating measures of change drivers on innovative IT partnerships.

5.2.2 Contribution to practice

- Artefact: We created an artefact for change drivers on modular aspects of innovative IT partnerships, and experts gave their feedback that several insights were already applied in practice, thus showing their practical added value.
- Illustrated Artefacts: To create more clarity and understanding, we detailed out three artefacts to illustrate the practical validity and applicability of the

construction model, quality attributes and mitigating and/or cultivating measures on change drivers.

5.3 Limitations

Below is a summary of the limitations identified in the research, organized with the most significant impact listed first.

- Due to the low number of experts and analysed change drivers this research is strongly qualitative. The findings of the interviews suggest a direction of the findings but not a statistically significant conclusion.
- High variability in the definitions of change drivers. Current change drivers do not have a concise definition. During the expert interviews we only explored relevant change drivers without having time to define brief and concise definitions. Change drivers are strongly related to construction elements in which the type of change is more important than a very precise definition of a specific change. Definitions for individual construction components, change drivers, and quality attributes are currently missing.
- Change drivers can have both negative and positive impacts; however, the assessment allowed for only a single response. During the experts' meeting, change drivers were evaluated using a Likert scale (1 for negative, 3 for neutral, and 5 for positive), with only one rating per driver based on the most recent experience.
- We consulted 10 experts during a panel discussion and conducted individual interviews with three separate experts. One expert participated in both the panel and an individual follow-up interview. The experts were sourced from the personal networks of the authors and professors, leading to potential bias. However, this was mitigated by including experts from five different industries and two different countries.
- We focused only on the “arrangement phase” and “generation phase” of the partnership contract lifecycle (Gambal et al., 2022). During the interviews we did not validate explicitly whether the findings are only applicable within these two phases.
- Several construction elements used to establish a partnership construction model have been validated. Only those elements relevant to the assessed change drivers have been confirmed. Therefore, the construction model in its entirety is only partially validated.

5.4 Suggestions for future research

Below is a summary of suggestions for future research, addressing the limitations and organized with the most significant recommendations listed first.

- Further research is needed to complete (1) relevant change drivers, (2) mitigating and cultivating measures and (3) construction model of a partnership.
- Change drivers could be analysed from a different perspective e.g. from an anti-fragility perspective.
- Modularity is limited in its applicability to the construction of a partnership, but it might be applicable to the implementation of innovation within a partnership.

- Current research focus on Change Drivers from the creation phase of a partnership. Exploitation phase could come with different change drivers which is interesting for future research.
- Future research should ask formal validation of the entire construction model and could include a follow-up study with these experts and re-validate their views or adjust where changes are appropriate.

5.5 Reflections

5.5.1 Perspective by Bernard de Veer

- Navigating through uncertainty is a recurring experience. It consistently challenges me mentally, demanding resilience, trust, and above all, curiosity.
- Engaging in scientific writing cultivates mastery. I realized that mere contemplation does not offer the same depth of understanding.
- Viewing systems through the lens of construction rather than functionality or implementation has enriched my perspective as an architect, enabling me to make a significant difference. Designing the construction of a system lays the groundwork for its success.
- The essence of a system often resides in its construction, which is frequently overlooked in favour of functionality or implementation. Crafting the right construction takes time, a process often misunderstood due to its abstract nature, yet it leads to sustainable and adaptable systems.
- Successful partnerships require an ecosystem mindset rather than an ego-system approach (Scharmer, 2013). This necessitates a long-term, holistic strategy where partners serve the partnership without compromising their own strengths.
- DEMO, with its associated theorems, provides a novel perspective. The focus of innovation shifts from data or information to transactions, indicating that the organization itself becomes the foundation of innovation.

5.5.2 Perspective by Serge van Nimwegen

- Enriching discussions with ‘management view’ versus ‘architectural view’, both between the authors as well as with many experts.
- Scoping and rescoping is a necessary part of the thesis journey to avoid ‘boiling the ocean’.
- Discovering and applying academic principles and theories such as exaptation or NST
- I really liked the part to get the experiences of the various experts and find the common ground
- I learned more about the various theories and layers of architecture so I can even better understand the perspective applied by my colleagues working in architecture.

6 Conclusion

This thesis explores strategic innovation within enterprises, focusing on the role of IT as an enabler and accelerator of competitive advantage. While IT outsourcing has historically driven innovation, challenges and risks persist, potentially linked to modularity issues. Traditional outsourcing contracts often limit innovation due to their transactional design, highlighting a need for insights on the strategic innovation aspect of innovative IT partnerships. The competitive landscape is shifting from transactional engagements towards innovative partnerships. Strategic innovations are seen as crucial for significantly enhancing a client's overall competitiveness, especially with the growing strategic importance of IT and the need for specialized skills and solutions.

The central research question investigated is: **What is the influence of modularity on the adaptability of innovative IT partnerships?** This question is broken down into three sub-questions focusing on relevant change drivers, the construction model of an innovative IT partnership, and the impact of modularity on quality attributes. The thesis mentions that innovation is inherently unpredictable and thus requires evolvability. Similarly, partnerships, as vehicles for innovation, must also be evolvable. Modularity, through design principles like maximizing interdependence within building blocks and minimizing it between them (high cohesion, low coupling), is seen as a way to enable this evolvability. Normalized Systems Theory (NST) is presented as a theory and set of design principles for creating evolvable information systems, which aims to prevent ripple effects or combinatorial effects by avoiding the combination of multiple concerns. The application of NST to innovative IT partnerships is explored as a form of exaptation.

The research employed a Design Science Research approach, combining academic rigor with practical relevance. The methodology involved a literature review, an expert panel discussion to collect relevant change drivers for partnerships from practice, and individual in-depth expert interviews. An artefact based on change drivers and a proposed modular construction model of a partnership was developed and refined through these expert interactions. The construction of a partnership (white-box) was analysed using the function-construction theory and elements were mapped to DEMO's structural elements.

Key findings include the **identification of relevant change drivers** for innovative IT partnerships through the expert panel. The panel also provided initial insights into the impact of these drivers and potential mitigating/cultivating measures. The thesis focused on three selected change drivers with the highest variability and a clear modular characteristic: Strategic Shift, Leaving Partner, and New Partner. The proposed construction model of a partnership, comprising elements like Shared goals, Partners, Contracts, Capabilities, and Innovation, was incrementally validated by experts in relation to these change drivers.

Regarding the impact of modularity, applying NST theories like Separation of Concerns (SoC) and Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC) to partnership construction elements provides a framework for understanding how change drivers impact the structure and for identifying measures to manage these impacts. Measures such as periodic synchronization meetings to align objectives (SoC, CCC, SoS) and managing knowledge sharing practices were discussed as ways to adhere to NST principles. Experts confirmed that this structured analysis using a modular/construction model can help to proactively address partnership dynamics.

A significant implication identified is the tension between the need for partner autonomy (which modularity, like SoC, supports for independence and innovation for that partner) and the need for interdependency and collaboration within a partnership (essential for synergy and joint innovation within the partnership). High modularity with strict boundaries, as advocated by some NST principles like SoC and CCC when applied strictly for isolation, might impede the necessary knowledge sharing and close collaboration required for partnership strength and innovation, leading to contradictory findings regarding capabilities. Successfully managing and balancing this paradox through shared understanding and a well-designed construction is crucial for partnership success. The role of NST in achieving an evolvable partnership *construction* itself appears limited; however, its strategic role in **aligning individual partners with the partnership's objectives and goals** (managing the autonomy/collaboration polarity) is notably strong.

This research contributes to science by applying NST to the new domain of innovative IT partnerships via exaptation, providing a foundation for systematic analysis. It also contributes by proposing a construction model for partnerships based on DEMO theory, collects initial change drivers, and explores measures for managing their impact from both architectural and managerial lenses. For practice, the developed change driver artefact and illustrated examples offer a structured way to analyse modular aspects of partnerships, confirmed by experts as having practical value.

Limitations include the qualitative nature and potential bias due to the low number of experts, the partial validation of the construction model, and the focus on specific phases of the partnership lifecycle. Future research suggestions include completing the collection of drivers, measures, and construction model elements, exploring other perspectives, applying modularity to the implementation phase, and conducting formal holistic validation.

In conclusion, the thesis demonstrates that applying modularity principles, particularly through the lens of Normalized Systems Theory, offers a valuable structured approach for analysing and enhancing the evolvability and adaptability of innovative IT partnerships when facing change drivers. However, successfully balancing the partner's autonomy needs with the interdependency within the partnership is crucial for fostering successful innovative IT partnerships.

Appendix A: References

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Appendix B: List of Tables

Table 2-1 Differences between flexibility, variability and evolvability (van Nuffel, 2011)....	14
Table 2-2 Overview quality attributes in an innovative partnership.....	28
Table 2-3 Characteristics of transactional collaboration versus innovative partnerships	30
Table 2-4 Partnership construction elements related to DEMO construction elements (Dietz & Mulder, 2024).....	33
Table 4-1 Background Experts in the Panel.....	39
Table 4-2 Initial collection change drivers.....	40
Table 4-3 Consolidated collection of change drivers.....	40
Table 4-4 Change drivers ordered by variability	41
Table 4-5 Change drivers from expert panel.....	43
Table 4-6 Background of the experts of the individual interviews.....	44

Appendix C: List of Figures

Figure 1-1 Conceptual Model	10
Figure 2-1 Relations between innovation and modularity	12
Figure 2-2 Innovation by partnerships	12
Figure 2-3 Evolvability, Flexibility, Variability (van Nuffel, 2011)	13
Figure 2-4 Competitive forces model (Porter, 1979)	17
Figure 2-5 Unstable system (Haerens, 2021)	22
Figure 2-6 Solution and Application Domain Matrix (Gregor & Hevner, 2013)	24
Figure 2-7 Partnership maturity curve (Mehta & Mehta, 2010)	25
Figure 2-8 FORT (Four Outsourcing Relationship Types) framework (Kishore et al., 2003)	26
Figure 2-9 Mapping the Reinforcing Cycles (Aubert et al., 2015)	27
Figure 2-10 Strategic innovation through outsourcing: integrative framework (Gambal et al., 2022)	29
Figure 2-11 Function - Construction - Implementation (Dietz & Mulder, 2024)	31
Figure 2-12 Organisation types and System orientations (Dipten and Mulder 2019)	33
Figure 2-13 Construction elements of a partnership (own work)	33
Figure 3-1 Based on Design Science (Gregor & Hevner, 2013)	34
Figure 3-2 Research design scope	34
Figure 3-3 Research process steps	35
Figure 3-4 Elements of change driver artefact model	37
Figure 3-5 Artefact template	37
Figure 4-1 Relevant construction components of a strategic shift	44
Figure 4-2 Relevant construction components of leaving partner	47
Figure 4-3 Relevant construction elements of new partner	49
Figure 5-1 Validated construction components	52
Figure 5-2 Discussion of architecture and managerial lens	53
Figure 5-3 Application NST on a partnership	56

Appendix D: Artefacts

Change driver: Strategic Shift

1 Description change driver Strategy of partnership or partners changed over time. This includes, among others, delivery of new types of products & services, change in product development).

2 Construction elements

3a Relevant NS theories:

- Separation of Concerns (SoC)** Partners are separate concerns in a partnership. When partners are isolated from one another, changes can be easily absorbed by one partner without impacting the others.
- Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC)** Every partner should comply with the strategic agreements, as any change in strategy affects each partner.
- Separation of State (SoS)** Agreements evolve over time as the partnership evolves. Each agreement represents a state that every partner should align with. Each version of an agreement is stored as a distinct state. Separation of State can be viewed as the Separation of Concerns over time.

3b Measures based on NST

- Periodic synchronization meetings are held to align with the shared objectives of the partnership (CCC) and the individual objectives of partners (SoC), thereby preventing unexpected departures.
- These periodic review sessions are a crucial element of the partnership agreement and are documented to ensure that all partners remain aligned over time (SoS).

4a Relevant Quality attributes for change driver on innovative partnerships

- Shared objectives** (Vitasek & Manrodt (2012), NZIOKA (2016) and Kranz (2021))
 - Partners actively collaborate which leads to mutual benefits (Vitasek & Manrodt (2012) and strengthening the partnership.
 - Partners are fully aligned with shared objectives (Vitasek & Manrodt (2012)). Not focus on HOW but on WHAT to unlock new opportunities for innovation and growth that might not be possible in more traditional transactional relationships (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)
 - Not focus on completing tasks only, but also **adding value to the relationship**.
- High interdependency** between partners to innovate due to the importance of relationship learning and joint innovation (Ven et al., 2010; Kranz, 2021).

4b Managerial measures

- Partners may unexpectedly leave the partnership when a mismatch occurs between the partnership's objectives and those of the individual partners.
- Development of opportunistic behavior which will weaken the partnership (Sun & Lo, 2014)

Legenda

- Sync meetings to align shared objectives with all partners

Change driver: Leaving partner

1 Description change driver

- Partner(s) may leave a partnership due to a variety of reasons: e.g. strategic shift of the partnership (expert panel) or a lack of shared benefits and risks (Lane & Lum, 2011; Alexandrov 2015)

2 Construction elements

3a Measures based on NST

- Separation of Concerns (SoC)** Partners are separate concerns in a partnership and can leave or enter the partnership. To drive innovation, a partnership needs specific capabilities. These capabilities should be developed independently of any changes occurring within or among partners, ensuring the partnership remains evolvable despite fluctuations in its composition.
- Cross-cutting Concerns (CCC)** All partners share benefits and risks within the partnership. Any alteration in this dynamic will affect every partner involved.

3b Mitigation/cultivation measures

- Support **knowledge** sharing and knowledge building to develop **capabilities** independently of any changes within or among partners (red circle).
- Continuous **align** capability building between partners to determine complementary or redundant capabilities needed for innovation.
- Define **notice period** when a partner announces its leave.
- No **poaching** of personnel.

4a Relevant quality attributes for change driver on innovative partnerships

- Co-creation of value** are essential to foster innovation in partnerships (Sun & Lo, 2014; Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012; Kranz, 2021)
- Mutually committed** to each others success (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012)

4b Managerial measures

- A lack in **capabilities** could potentially disrupt the development of innovative activities (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012).
- Diminished trust** resulting from partners' lack of demonstrated commitment (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012; Mehta & Mehta, 2010)

Legenda

- Sync meetings for capability management

Change driver: New partner

1 Description change driver

- A partners may join a partnership for a variety of reasons. E.g., lack of needed capabilities and technology (Gopal and Gosain, 2010; Levina and Vaast, 2005) or market access.
- A new partner necessitates the redistribution of shared benefits and risks. Proper distribution is crucial to maintaining high commitment among partners.

3a Relevant NS theories:

- **Separation of Concerns (SoC)** Partners are separate concerns in a partnership and can leave or enter the partnership. To drive innovation, new partner can enter the partnership for needed complementary **capabilities**.
- **Cross-Cutting Concerns (CCC)** All partners share benefits, risks and funding. A change on of these will impact all partners in the partnership.

3b Measures based on NST

- **Periodic review sync meeting** to align with **shared benefits** of partnership and benefits of partners when new partners join the partnership agreement.
- The allocation of benefits and risks is dependent on the nature of the delivered capability (commodity versus core).

4a Relevant quality attributes for change driver for innovative partnerships

1. **Shared benefits and risks** are fundamental for partnerships (Vitasek & Manrodt, 2012; Lane & Lum, 2011; Alexandrova, 2015; Gambal et al., 2022).
2. A new partner can bring new knowledge and experience which can foster innovation. This has a positive effect on joint innovation and transfer ideas (Weeks and Feeny, 2008) needed for capability development and innovation (Ven et al., 2010).

4b Managerial measures

- Changes in financial arrangements, including shared benefits & risks (Lane & Lum, 2011), or funding, can result in misalignments in financial agreements among partners, potentially leading to imbalance within the partnership.

Legenda

- Sync meetings for benefit & risks alignment

Appendix E: Research results - Construction model

Change Driver	Construction model
Structure	Describe per change driver (per row) the used construction elements. Excluding the proposed structure as it reflects the measures implemented to ensure compliance with NST (See Appendix F: Research results - Measures based on NST and Managerial measures)
Strategic shift	<p>The following construction components are identified and validated by experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shared goals and objectives (strategy): Experts validated this component and stated that changes in shared goals and objectives within partnerships should explicitly be discussed in a structured manner. - Contracts: Experts validated this component and stated that they should include both fixed and flexible elements to support adaptability and manage change, beyond simply minimizing risk. - Partners: Experts validated partner components. <p>Experts stated that the construction model make elements explicit, facilitating better understanding and management.</p>
Leaving partner	<p>The following construction components are identified and validated by experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners: Experts validated partner components as an essential means for innovation. - Innovation: Experts validated the innovation as an output of the partnership. - Capabilities (knowledge and expertise): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Own work and experts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Experts have validated this component, highlighting that sharing capabilities among multiple partners is essential for strengthening the partnership. o Expert interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Two types of capabilities exist. Capabilities needed for the partnership and capabilities belonging to partners. ▪ Avoid managing partnership capabilities in isolation, as it can impede innovation. Promoting overlapping capabilities is more important than focusing solely on continuity and stability, as it fosters a more innovative environment. ▪ It is essential to distinguish between core and commodity capabilities in the partnership construction. <p>Experts stated that the construction model make elements explicit, facilitating better understanding and management.</p>
New partner	<p>The following construction components are identified and validated by experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners: Experts validated this component.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Shared benefits & risks: Experts validated this component. Changes in benefits and risks might impact all partners. <p>Experts have indicated that the construction model enhances clarity in partnerships. Through modularity, the construction model facilitates a structured and precise evaluation of partnerships, aiding in the establishment of a stable foundation that remains resilient amid variability.</p>
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Appendix F: Research results - Measures based on NST and Managerial measures

Change Driver	Measures to comply with NS theories (3B)	Managerial measures (4B)
	<p>Validate whether modularity (NST) can be applied on the construction of partnerships.</p> <p>Mitigate the impact of a change driver through measures that ensure compliance with NST.</p> <p>For each change driver (listed per row), describe the measure(s) to comply with NST.</p>	<p>For each change driver (listed per row), describe the relevant quality attributes and the managerial measures identified during the expert meetings.</p>
Strategic shift	<p>Regular Synchronization Meetings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Own work and expert interviews: A strategic shift of the partnership results in change of shared objectives and goals for all partners (CCC). Implementing regular synchronization meetings are crucial for aligning the shared objectives of the partnership and the individual objectives of partners (SoC). These meetings (proxies) help prevent unexpected departures by ensuring both collective and individual goals are regularly reviewed and aligned. This prevents ripple effects through the partnership. ○ Additional findings from Expert Interviews: Often, the strategic objectives of partners and partnerships are not explicitly and frequently discussed, making these meetings vital for fostering open communication and adaptability. <p>Documenting Agreements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Own work and expert interviews: Own work and expert interviews states that changes in strategy must documented in agreements to provide a historical reference for previous decisions and supports partnership evolvability. This approach separates changes in strategic agreements and facilitates a clear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Shared objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expert interview: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Adaptability in Strategic Shifts: Expert interviews highlight that strategic shifts can impact all aspects of the partnership, sometimes necessitating a complete restart. It is crucial for tactical elements to remain adaptable to accommodate these shifts. While the overarching strategy may remain constant, its implementation can change, requiring flexibility in the partnership's operations. ▪ Recognition and Gratitude: Incorporating explicit arrangements for recognition and gratitude into contracts can help reinforce positive relationships and collaboration during strategic shifts. This approach fosters a supportive environment that encourages partners to navigate changes together. ▪ Managing Mismatches and Opportunistic Behaviour: Literature suggests that unexpected departures can occur when there is a mismatch between the objectives of the partner and the partnership. This can lead to opportunistic behaviour, which weakens the partnership. Addressing these

	<p>transition between contract versions, enhancing decoupling between changes (SoS).</p>	<p>mismatches proactively is essential to maintain partnership stability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High interdependency: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expert interview: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Involvement of Diverse Partners: Adjusting tactics during strategic shifts may require the involvement of various types of partners. Major partners can benefit from collaboration with smaller, innovative partners to achieve strategic objectives. Recognizing the equal significance of each partner is crucial for the partnership's success.
<p>Leaving partner</p>	<p>Distributed capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Own work and expert interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The departure of a partner may lead to certain capabilities becoming unavailable and impacts the full partnership and partners (CCC). As capabilities within partnerships are essential for innovation, they should be managed as a unified construction component (SoC). For reasons of continuity and stability, capabilities must be distributed across multiple partners. ○ Implement knowledge sharing and governance by ensuring that each partner has a representative within each capability to minimize ripple effect of this CCC within the partnership. This also promotes effective governance. - Expert interviews: Experts stated that duplication of capabilities among partners must be avoided due to high costs. Usually, this is also not possible because a partnership is created due to a lack of specific capabilities. <p>Isolated capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Own work: The departure of a partner may lead to certain capabilities becoming unavailable. Develop stable and autonomous capabilities by minimizing interdependencies with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Disruption of Innovative Activities: Literature indicates that changes in capabilities due to a partner leaving can disrupt the continuity of innovative activities. It's essential to address these disruptions to maintain the partnership's innovative momentum. ○ Prevent poaching: when a partner leaves, there may be attempts to hire expertise from remaining partners. This can impact partnership dynamics and resource distribution, necessitating careful management to maintain balance. Establishing a grace period before a partner can leave and defining policies to prevent poaching between partners can mitigate negative impacts of departures and stabilize the partnership. ○ Identify maturity levels: The maturity level of partners plays a significant role in the partnership, affecting collaboration effectiveness and adaptability to change. It's important to consider partner maturity when managing departures. ○ Facilitate knowledge sharing: Encouraging knowledge sharing can help foster capabilities within the partnership. - Mutually committed

	<p>other capabilities. This approach aids in the effective maintenance and development of capabilities (SoC).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert interviews: Avoid managing partnership capabilities in isolation, as it can impede innovation. Promoting overlapping partnership capabilities is more important than focusing solely on continuity and stability, as it fosters a more innovative environment. <p>Legal role in partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert interviews: The role of legal is vital in strengthening partnerships by assessing partner contributions and bridging differences, thereby maintaining a focus on partnership growth rather than solely on minimizing risks. <p>Guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert interviews: Create guidelines, serving as contract, to flexibly manage situations rather than relying on rigid boundaries. These guidelines accommodate varying circumstances and promote resilience within the partnership. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Disruption of innovative activities: See description above. ○ Prevent poaching: see description above. ○ Facilitate knowledge sharing: see description above. ○ Apply good leaver, bad leaver principle: It's crucial to manage leaving partners effectively to ensure that the partnership remains balanced. Applying the good leaver, bad leaver principle can be beneficial. Recognizing that a partner's departure may be advantageous depending on the context, clear agreements regarding leaving partners can strengthen commitment. ○ Facilitate partnership journey: Viewing the partnership as a journey, supported by clear agreements for both positive and challenging times, emphasizes shared goals over capability-driven objectives. This perspective fosters long-term commitment and resilience.
New partner	<p>Regular synchronization meetings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Own work and expert interviews: New partners impacts shared benefits and risks agreed on in the partnership and impact all partners (CCC). Regular synchronization meetings to align shared benefits and risks are essential to manage these changes as they function as a proxy between individual partners and the partnership. The allocation of benefits and risks is influenced by the type of capability (core or commodity) offered by the partner. <p>Proactive agreements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert interviews: Establish agreements regarding the entry and exit of partners, addressing both success and failure scenarios. Though often overlooked, this proactive approach is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shared benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manage change: that introducing a new partner can bring uncertainty and potentially increase conflict within the partnership. This necessitates a re-evaluation of various aspects, including contractual agreements that clearly outline shared risks and benefits to manage these potential issues. ○ Manage change in cost structure and competition: Expert interviews reveal that a new partner affects the cost structure and competitive dynamics, impacting all partners. It's important to assess these changes to ensure the partnership remains balanced and competitive. - New knowledge and experience:

	<p>vital for effectively managing transitions when partners join or leave.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Manage alignment and communication: Continuous alignment and communication are critical for maintaining the quality and cohesion of the partnership. Regularly revisiting and aligning shared goals and strategies can help integrate the new partner effectively.○ Value assessment: New partners can play a pivotal role in ensuring partnership success. Value assessments should consider the partnership as a whole rather than focusing solely on individual entities. This holistic approach helps leverage the strengths of all partners.○ Strengthening Partnership Over Fairness: Prioritizing the strengthening of the partnership is more important than ensuring a 'fair' distribution of benefits and risks. Fairness should be viewed in the context of contributing to the overall partnership's robustness and success.
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Appendix G: List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AVT	Action Version Transparency
BEEM	Basic Enterprise Engineering Map
CCC	Cross Cutting Concern
CD	Change Driver
CE	Combinatorial Effects
DEMO	Design and Engineering Methodology for Organizations
DVT	Data Version Transparency
GSS	Group Support System
IS	Information System
IT	Information Technology
NS	Normalised Systems
NST	Normalised Systems Theory
SoC	Separation of Concerns
SoS	Separation of States
TAO	Teleology, Affordances and Ontology,

Appendix H: Recordings expert panel and expert interviews

Content	Link
Expert Panel	Recording: Link Transcript: Innovative Partnerships and Drivers of Change-3.pdf
Expert interview 1 (Sales Manager)	Recording: Link Transcript: Duo thesis & draft artifact Transcript Expert 20250311.docx
Expert interview 2 (Enterprise Architect)	Recording: Link Transcript: Duo thesis & draft artifact expert.docx
Expert interview 3 (Enterprise Architect/Manager)	Recording: Link Transcript: Innovative partnerships.docx
Expert interview 4 (CEO)	Recording: Link Transcript: Notes Expert interview 3 April 2025 16h00.docx